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The Effect of Revision Following Teacher's Indirect Written Corrective Feedback on Learners' L2 Grammatical Accuracy in EFL Writing Classes

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Declaration

I hereby declare that this dissertation/thesis entitled: "The Effect of Revision Following Teacher's Indirect Written Corrective Feedback on Learners' L2 Grammatical Accuracy in EFL Writing Classes" is my own original work and hereby certify that unless stated, all work contained within this is my own independent research and has not been submitted for the award of any other degree at any institution, except where due acknowledgement is made in the text.

A handwritten signature in blue ink, consisting of a stylized capital letter 'R' followed by a horizontal line that tapers to the right.

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This dissertation/thesis has been written under my supervision and has been submitted for the award of the degree of "Master of Arts' in 'Applied Linguistics / TESOL' with my approval as supervisor.

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Examining Committee Certification

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Dedication

I dedicate this thesis to my dear parents and my wife who are the source of inspiration and power.

Rebaz

2023

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Abstract

Teachers of English as a Foreign Language (EFL) often provide Written Corrective Feedback (WCF) due to its contribution to Second Language (L2) writing development. However, many students do not take the provided WCF into consideration. Accordingly, some researchers believe that WCF, along with revision may engage the students in the process of error correction and make the provided feedback more effective. Even though many studies have examined the efficacy of WCF, their contributions to the mediating role of revision are minimal and inconclusive due to methodological or design flaws and no studies have been conducted on this topic in the Kurdistan Region of Iraq (KRI). Therefore, the current study examines the impact of revision following WCF on improving EFL undergraduate Kurdish students' writing accuracy and whether this impact can be transferred to new writing pieces. Furthermore, it investigates whether various types of grammatical features (article system, subject /verb agreement, and verb form) are equally influenced by the revision practice. It further explores the perception of the subject teacher towards the process of revision and its effect on students' writing performance. To achieve these aims, the study employed a mixed-method design for data collection and analysis. The quantitative data was collected using a quasi-experimental design in which fifty second-year English students from a KRI public university were assigned as treatment (revised their writing based on WCF) and control groups (only checked the WCF without revising their writing). Following the treatment, a semi-structured interview with the subject teacher was conducted to secure the qualitative data. The data were analysed using SPSS and thematic analysis. The results of the quantitative phase revealed that revision of the writing tasks enhances their L2 writing grammatical accuracy and its effect is persistent in new writing pieces over time. A further finding was that the impact level of revision varied from one grammatical feature to another. Relatedly, it was also concluded from the qualitative data that demanding students to revise is effective in fostering engagement and motivation for both students and teachers. This study contributes to raising awareness among stakeholders on how to integrate and employ WCF and revision into the educational process.

Keywords: Written Corrective Feedback, revision, grammatical accuracy, teachers, students.

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List of Abbreviations

KRI	Kurdistan Region of Iraq
IL	Interlanguage
L2	Second language
SLA	Second language acquisition
SSI	Semi-structured interviews
ESL	English as a second language
EFL	English as a foreign language
TLS	Target-Like Structure
ZPD	Zone of Proximal Development
CF	Corrective Feedback
WCF	Written Corrective Feedback
EC	Error Correction
GF	Grammatical Features
AS	Article System
SVA	Subject Verb Agreement
VF	Verb Form

Chapter 1: Introduction

This chapter presents the introduction of the study where the problem of the study is first introduced. Secondly, it discusses the significance of the study. The objectives of the study and the research questions are then outlined. Finally, the thesis organization is presented.

1.1 Statement of the Problem

Recently, contrary to four decades ago, writing has received more attention in the field of second language acquisition (Hyland, 2003). The reason behind it is that primarily Second Language (L2) users' learning, work and intellect are judged based on their writing (Klimova, 2013). Also, effective writing assists the students in conveying their messages and ideas more successfully in the academic context. However, learning to write effectively is more difficult than acquiring the other three language skills because it requires more extensive instruction and learning techniques (Brown & Lee, 2015). As such, they further state that in order to become a proficient writer, one needs to be literate and have an instructor. Therefore, it can be noticed that many of the L2 students are able to speak the language fluently but unable to write efficiently and this is even true for native speakers too.

English as a Foreign Language (EFL) university students in the Kurdistan Region of Iraq are not exempt from this situation, and many of them struggle with their writing tasks (Ahmed, 2019) and want to improve their level, but they are unsure of where the deficiencies lie and how to fix them. In the KRI, despite studying English since the first grade in school and having writing classes in the university, still Kurdish EFL writers' writing skills are low due to having linguistic problems and producing incomprehensible language (Abdulmajeed, 2016). As such, learners need more instruction on how to become better writers, yet there are many challenges facing instructors while teaching writing. One of these challenges is that many students cannot notice the input they are receiving from the class to convert it to uptake and contribute to their Second Language Acquisition (SLA). A practical solution to this is the provision of Written Corrective Feedback (WCF), where students need to take care of the input (Rassaei & Moinzadah, 2011). The reason is, while writing, students make errors, and these errors will be corrected by the instructor (input), which in return facilitates L2 learning. Moreover, Ellis (2009) states that CF assists learners in understanding their weaknesses and strengths because their flaws are diagnosed, and the techniques for approaching them are also provided. In this respect, teachers' WCF can serve as clear

guidelines to indicate the types of errors and their appropriate corrections; otherwise, students cannot overcome their weaknesses.

Although many teachers provide WCF to their students, few of them are equipped well with a systematic method for the provision of CF in how, where and when to provide feedback (Galaly, 2017; Najmaddin, 2010). Each of CF types (Implicit vs. Explicit and Focused vs. unfocused) can be useful in some contexts based on the need, background, and level of the learners, while ineffective in some other contexts (Bitchener & Knoch, 2016).

In implicit feedback, the error is underlined or marked with an asterisk, but the students are not given the correct form and must figure it out themselves. In contrast, explicit written corrective feedback (WCF) provides students with the correct form of the error (Bitchener & Ferris, 2012). Ekanayaka and Ellis (2020) state that both types have advantages and disadvantages. When it comes to the implicit WCF, according to Ekanayaka and Ellis (2020), the advantage is that it forces the students to go deeper in processing the error, which may lead to “facilitating linguistic development” (p.3). As for the explicit WCF, the advantage is that there is no ambiguity and students directly receive the correct form while the disadvantage is that it is easy to process, thus “students fail to identify the rules or regularities underlying the corrections” (Ekanayaka & Ellis, 2020, p. 3).

The second category in providing WCF is whether to be focused (selective) or unfocused (comprehensive). According to Ellis et al. (2008, as cited in Frear & Chiu, 2015), focused WCF is to provide feedback “on one or a few pre-selected structures” (p.24) while the unfocused one deals with all the errors in the whole writing task. These two types of WCF, like the other types, have positive and negative aspects. For example, the unfocused WCF increases the attentional load and becomes more difficult for the learner to attend to the structure unlike the focused one (Sheen, 2007), while Anderson (2010) reported that in unfocused CF content teachers could also comment on linguistic errors, which will also save learners from confusion if part of their errors were corrected while other errors were not. On the other hand, with focused feedback, the issue is that it only deals with certain aspects of writing errors and neglects the rest (Frear & Chiu, 2015). However, it has an advantage that students appear to be more open to receiving corrections aimed towards a single or small number of error categories rather than a huge number of them as it removes the attentional load on the learners (Ellis et al., 2008). Considering the above-mentioned pros and cons,

a majority of the studies cited above have favoured focused WCF over unfocused WCF (Bitchener, 2008). It is because it does not overload the learner and allows for more efficient processing of feedback, which contributes to better learning (Sheen, 2007). Hence, the present study employed focused WCF in light of these arguments.

Moreover, even once CF is provided, many students do not pay attention to it and ignore it, thereby demotivating teachers to continue to proceed with the provision of WCF to their students. As such the need to ask students to revise their writings arises to make the provided CF more effective in L2 writing learning. Liu and Brown (2015) state that a powerful solution to students' ignoring the provided CF is to engage them in the process of correction by asking them to revise their draft based on the teachers' CF. Additionally, according to Ellis (2004, as cited in Soltanpour & Valizadeh, 2018) the add-on effect of revision can lead to learning of a particular feature and can be regarded as the first step into developing writing quality because the students will be held accountable for their writing and have more time to think which allows learners to better attend the correct form and regularity of the errors. Moreover, Ellis (2009; 2010a) points out that revision requirement motivates students by informing them of their progress and assisting teachers understand the extent of their teaching effectiveness. Ellis (2009) further states that asking students to revise their writing is an interesting necessary step towards facilitating language development since the learners will be more attentive to corrections. Furthermore, regarding the focus of revision and WCF, the vast majority of L2 writers (especially Kurdish EFL writers) make mistakes in grammatical structures. Mahmood (2016) found that Kurdish EFL students are most prone to making grammatical errors when testing 30 English language students at the University of Suleimani. In another study by Aziz, Ahmed, and Salim (2021), the same result confirmed that Kurdish EFL writers most commonly make grammatical errors. Thus, they suggest paying more attention to grammatical errors in EFL Kurdish, particularly through the use of WCF. Moreover, according to the results of a study conducted by Ahmed (2020) in a KRI university, "Kurdish EFL learners didn't know how to write suitable rules in the right place and how to deal with syntactic structure" (p. 166). As a result, the WCF and revision should focus primarily on grammatical errors. Hence, it is important to study the effect of revision on improving L2 students' grammatical accuracy, so the purpose of this study is to address this by providing and utilising indirect focused WCF.

1.2 Significance of the Study

In the Kurdistan Region of Iraq (KRI), many EFL university students score low marks in their writing tasks (Ahmed, 2019) and wish to improve their writing level, but they do not know where the shortcomings are and how to start improving them. Therefore, teachers' WCF can act as clear guidelines to indicate the errors, their types, and relevant corrections; otherwise, the students cannot turn their weaknesses into strengths. However, still many English language teachers complain that their students do not pay attention to the provided WCF; therefore, teachers become less motivated to proceed with practicing it. This issue can be resolved by asking students to revise their writing tasks after receiving WCF to ensure they notice the gap, attend the form, and learn the structure. Soltanpour and Valizadah (2018) argue that "during revision, learners are able to access their explicit L2 knowledge and notice the gap between it and their first draft production" (p. 1).

This study illustrates the importance of providing WCF and asking students to revise in order to influence teachers' and students' attitudes toward the use and benefits of this practice. It also guides the teachers about the mechanism of implementing WCF and asking their students to revise their writing. As such, it supports the educational environment as a whole in how to improve L2 students' writing accuracy.

Although numerous studies have been conducted about the effectiveness of WCF, many of them have design and methodological gaps which makes this study a significant attempt at the provision of WCF and requiring students to revise. Concerning the studies in the context of KRI (Chaqmaqchee, 2015; Galaly, 2017; Hama & Ismael, 2018; Mahmood, 2019; Najmaddin, 2010), none of them have investigated the add-on effect of revision on the provided WCF. Moreover, other than Abbas and Tawfeeq (2018a, 2018b) who have employed experimental design to study the impact of WCF, the rest of the researchers have attempted to find out the impact of WCF only through studying the perceptions of teachers and students. While, according to Bitchener and Ferris (2012), in order to arrive at reliable results, this practice needs to be studied over time in an experimental design via the means of pre-test and post-test. Although Abbas and Tawfeeq (2018b) made attempts to investigate the effect of WCF followed by revision, they did not directly address the influence of revision in enhancing grammatical accuracy of L2 students writing. Therefore, this study provides new insights into the role of revision after the provided WCF on the students' writing accuracy through experimental study. Therefore, this study will be the first attempt in the

KRI context to investigate the effect of revision after the provided WCF on the students' writing accuracy through experimental study.

When it comes to the studies in contexts other than KRI, there are studies that lack a control group or the control group has been used only for a short period of time (one-shot treatment) (Ferris, 1997; Polio, Fleck & Leder, 1998; Poorebrahim, 2017), while the current research examines the concept over time in an experimental design to test whether the impact can be long term and can be transferred to new pieces of writing. Furthermore, since most of the previously cited literature indicates that indirect feedback is more effective than direct feedback, and most of the other revision research have examined direct WCF plus revision, as such, the current study attempts to test the use of indirect WCF plus revision.

Therefore, this study provides clear insights into the practicality and usefulness of WCF and revision to teachers who struggle with their students to improve their low writing skills. Additionally, it will pave the way to motivate students and assist them in indicating their errors and shortcomings to improve their writing accuracy and proficiency. This will also help the ministry of higher education provide guidelines for teachers to prepare their students for their writing, allowing them to become proficient writers.

1.3 Objectives

The purpose behind this study is to examine the add-on effect of requiring students to revise their writing after receiving WCF on improving grammatical accuracy of their L2 writing. Furthermore, the aim is to find out if this practice can have long-term effects that can be transferred to new pieces of writing. Through this, it can be observed whether or not revising the written task can reduce grammatical errors in new written activities and assignments.

Another purpose is to investigate if practicing revision after receiving WCF can be more effective for certain grammatical features or if the impact will be the same. In addition, it is an attempt to examine the perception of the course teacher about the role of revision in students writing accuracy, and in which ways the revision was an (in)effective practice to improve the grammatical accuracy of students writing. And to what extent students were applying the comments in the revised versions.

1.4 Research Questions

The above-mentioned aims could be achieved by answering the following research questions as they have guided this study:

1. What is the effect of Indirect Corrective Feedback (ICF) with revision on the grammatical accuracy of L2 students' writing?
2. What is the long-term effect of ICF with revision on the improvement of L2 students' grammatical accuracy?
3. How does revision affect different types of grammatical features of L2 students' writing?
4. What is the perception of teachers towards the process and effect of revision on students' writing?

1.5 Organization of the Thesis

This thesis is made up of five chapters. Chapter one represents the introduction of the study where the problem of the study, the significance of the research, its objectives and the research questions are presented. Chapter two provides a review of the literature where key concepts and theories are introduced. Further, the literature review chapter tackles and discusses the debate about the efficacy of CF, the theoretical and empirical relevant background, and the main gaps in the literature. Chapter three sheds light on the methodology and design of the study to explain the procedure of data collection and data analysis. Chapter four presents the analysis of the data, and the main findings then discusses the findings of the research questions in association with the relevant theories and empirical results in the literature. The last chapter draws attention to the conclusion of the study where the findings and implications are summarized besides presenting the limitation of the study and recommendations for further research.

Chapter 2: Literature Review

2.1 Introduction

The purpose of this chapter is to provide theoretical knowledge about the key concepts of the current study, including corrective feedback (CF), written corrective feedback (WCF), and types of WCF. First, it discusses the importance of improving accuracy when writing in a second language. Thereafter, literature on CF and WCF is presented addressing the most effective types, as well as their role in improving L2 writing accuracy. After that, it examines the relevant literature to investigate teacher and student perceptions of WCF and which errors to correct. It is then followed by a review of the literature on the mediating role of asking learners to revise their writing following WCF. Finally, the chapter identifies the research gaps that exist in previous studies that have been conducted in various contexts.

2.2 Second Language (L2) Writing

The importance of writing in second language learning and teaching has received considerable attention over the past four decades (Hyland, 2003). This is due to the fact that a good command of writing skills equips the learners to successfully interact and communicate their ideas and information in the academic context and in the global world as the new global world is more driven by text (Zhu, 2004). However, learning to write is one of the most challenging aspects of L2 learning, it is such even for the first language speakers because unlike speaking it requires extensive instruction in how to write effectively (Brown & Lee, 2015). As such, Brown and Lee (2015) compare writing to swimming as these two are “culturally specific learned behaviours” (p. 426). One learns to swim if there is a swimming area and someone instructs you how to swim, similarly, people can learn how to compose a text if they are literate, and they have an instructor. Therefore, L2 writing classes have received major attention in order to prepare L2 learners to become proficient writers.

There are generally two different approaches to teaching writing which are either process-oriented or product Oriented (Sun & Feng, 2009). The product-oriented approach, as the name suggests, is about the final product of the writing where the teacher assigns a topic to the students and expects to receive a final product without any intervention during the process of writing (Nunan, 1999).

In this approach, the focus is mainly on the accurate use of structures i.e., linguistic features rather than on the meaning and “quality of ideas” (Hyland, 2003, p.2) as it is the case in the process approach (Tangkiengsirisin, 2006). According to Hyland (2003), there are four stages involved in teaching writing in product-oriented approach which are:

1. **Familiarization:** Learners are taught certain grammar and vocabulary, usually through a text.
2. **Controlled writing:** Learners manipulate fixed patterns, often from substitution tables.
3. **Guided writing:** Learners imitate model texts.
4. **Free writing:** Learners use the patterns they have developed to draft an essay, letter, and so forth. (p.4)

The student writer is expected to follow the previously learned rules of language and imitate them where the role of the teacher is that of an examiner who marks the written part and deals with it as the final product (Tangkiengsirisin, 2006). This sort of assessment is summative where the student does not have another chance to get back to his/her product (i.e., writing) to revise and improve it based on the teacher’s assessment and feedback (Hyland, 2003).

On the other hand, in the process-oriented approach of writing, time is required for classroom activities and classroom interactions before submitting the final product where the focus is on the process of writing such as providing feedback to arrive at a better and more polished product (Nunan, 1999). According to Matsuda (2003), in this approach, the main focus is on the writer rather than being on the text where the writer is expected to discover meaning in the process of writing with the help of the teacher as the facilitator and feedback provider. The assessment provided here is rather formative where the students can revise their writings based on the teacher’s comments through a series of classroom activities (Sun & Feng, 2009). According to Hyland (2003), the classroom activities in this approach to writing can take the following model:

Selection of topic: by teacher and/or students

Prewriting: brainstorming, collecting data, note taking, outlining, etc.

Composing: getting ideas down on paper

Response to draft: teacher/peers respond to ideas, organization, and style

Revising: reorganizing, style, adjusting to readers, refining ideas

Response to revisions: teacher/peers respond to ideas, organization, and style.

Proofreading and editing: checking and correcting form, layout, evidence, etc.

Evaluation: teacher evaluates progress over the process

Publishing: by class circulation or presentation, noticeboards, Website, etc.

Follow-up tasks: to address weaknesses. (p.11)

As these interactions and classroom activities are of significant value in facilitating learning of L2 writing, thus, the process-oriented approach of writing has gained more attention as compared to the product-oriented approach (Nemouchi, 2008, as cited in Sheir et al., 2015). In the same vein, Archibald and Jeffery (2000) highlight that many of the studies about writing have dealt with the writing process and they have classified the process of writing as planning, translating (converting the plan into text) and reviewing it. Moreover, they keep stating that planning and reviewing are more focused and emphasized than actual writing (converting the ideas into text). Therefore, the researcher of the current study focuses on the last phase of writing which is the reviewing process. Although several activities can assist learners to review their writings, the focus here will be on the major activity which is the provision of corrective feedback (CF). Therefore, the following section will be a Theoretical Framework (TF) about CF and its role in L2 writing learning.

2.3 Theoretical Framework about CF and its Role in Enhancing L2 Writing Accuracy

Classroom interactions in the EFL classes are of immense value for providing massive input to facilitate L2 learning. However, if this input, despite its vitality in SLA, is not noticed by the learners might not lead to acquiring the complex and demanding structures (Rassaei & Moinzadah, 2011). Therefore, compensation for such challenges, according to the micro cognitive perspective and L2 acquisition theories (Li, 2017) can be achieved through certain techniques and CF is one of them. Then, what is CF? What is its role? How are these benefits achieved?

According to Long (1996) corrective feedback can be divided into both negative feedback and positive feedback. Chaudron (1977, as cited in Sheen, 2004) defines CF is any sort of teacher reaction to disapprove or correct any type of learner errors. Additionally, Sheen asserts that the term CF is a blanket term used to refer to any implicit or explicit negative feedback to correct learners while producing any ungrammatical or unacceptable outputs in the target language (p.264). In the same vein, Spada and Lightbown (2010) state that CF is “an indication to a learner that his or her use of the target language is incorrect” (p. 216). Moreover, Lamberg (1980) defines CF as “information on performance which affects subsequent performance by influencing students’ attention to particular matters so that those matters undergo a change in the subsequent performance” (p.60). As stated earlier, in simple words, CF is the act of error correction by the teachers to improve the level of subsequent performances. What has been described is “Negative Feedback” which could be any explicit or implicit comment from the teacher to correct a learner’s incorrect use of language or as described by Hino (2006), it is “feedback to learners that informs them of their lack of success in L2 production” (p.1).

On the other hand, there is also Positive Feedback which is defined as the teacher’s confirmation that the learner’s output is correct (Ayhan, et. Al, 2011). According to Ani (2019), for students’ learning to be strengthened, it is vital that they receive positive feedback concerning their performance.

In the past, researchers considered errors as sinful acts and harmful to language learning; therefore, they believed that they should be completely avoided (e.g., Lado, 1957).

It was also believed that correction of errors or negative feedback would not be useful in the SLA, hence only positive feedback should be used (e.g., Chomsky, 1957; Krashen, 1985). This view, however, was proved to be incorrect by later studies and researchers as making errors is an integral and natural part of learning a second language (e.g., Long, 1996). Furthermore, he asserts that learners will improve their accuracy if they receive negative feedback, and that positive feedback alone will not suffice. Hence, the current study focuses on negative feedback which is referred to in different terminologies in literature (CF, negative feedback, negative evidence, or error correction) that are used interchangeably here (Mackey et al., 2000).

When it comes to the role of CF, many researchers have discussed numerous benefits. Generally, CF can act as a facilitator in two aspects which are “learning to write” and “writing to learn” (Boughey, 1997). The former role is when students practice writing and revise it to become better writers and learn to edit (Chandler, 2003). The latter is when the learners write in order to learn the language because as they write they make errors that will be corrected by the instructor via CF which in return contributes to SLA (Ellis et al., 2008).

Long (1996) states that CF can act as a valuable opportunity to create the chance for interaction to negotiate meaning which assists the learners to attend to the form and structure of the input. Furthermore, Ellis (2005) states that CF assists L2 learners to produce more target-like outputs because it makes them aware of their weaknesses by providing the correct form or techniques on how to correct themselves. Ellis (2005) explains that CF does not only make learners aware of their weaknesses, but also how to enhance their strengths.

The contribution of CF to L2 learning can be better understood when related to the micro cognitive perspective of input processing proposed by Gass (1997). Based on this perspective, input processing passes through five steps which are noticing the input, understanding it, turning the input into intake, internalization of the learned structure through practicing, and modified output (uptake) (Gass, 1997). In this section, only the first three stages will be described while the last two steps which are internalization and uptake, will be elaborated in section 2.9 when dealing with the role of revision.

According to Schmidt (1990) noticing is the state of consciousness and awareness about the input. The second step which is understanding is the process where the learner

analyses the noticed input to make sense of it (Li, 2017). As far as the third stage “intake” is concerned, it is defined by VanPatten (2002) “as the linguistic data actually processed from the input and held in working memory for further processing” (p. 757). Alternatively, if input is not processed and understood, it will not turn into intake (Li, 2017).

When students make errors, this shows the mismatch between their interlanguage (IL) and the target-like structure (TLS). According to Yule (2022) interlanguage is an “in-between system used in the L2 acquisition process that certainly contains aspects of the L1 and L2, but which is an inherently variable system with rules of its own” (p.167). Once the teacher provides his/her WCF on these errors, this will act as explicit knowledge. This explicit knowledge in return will assist the students to cognitively process the WCF input and learn from it. In the first stage, the students’ attention is drawn to the erroneous structure where they notice the gap between what they know and what they need to know which as a result will assist them to be aware about the provided input and notice the structure. According to the Noticing Hypothesis proposed by Schmidt in 1990 (Schmidt, 2012), only the noticed input becomes a learnt structure (intake). In other words, the provided input (in this case, the corrected structure) is only learned when noticed, which is stimulated by the CF and revision request.

According to Ferris (2003), once the structures are noticed (attended) by the students, this allows them to turn the received CF knowledge into comprehensible input. The input hypothesis was developed by Krashen in the 1970s (Cook & Cook, 1993) which he describes as learners’ exposure to an input which is slightly above their current knowledge as such, they understand and learn the corrected structure. Furthermore, based on Krashen’s Monitor Model (Cook & Cook, 1993), when students are exposed to comprehensible input, this learnt structure acts as a monitor to provide modified output, which in return facilitates L2 competence increase.

This is as far as the learners are concerned, but CF also assists the teachers in their teaching because it informs them about their learners’ needs and how to modify their teaching to meet their needs and gaps (Dabboub, 2019). Therefore, McDonough (2005) states that due to CF’s contribution to L2 learning, it needs to be added properly to language education. With that being stated, other aspects of CF need to be discussed such as the types and sources of CF which will be elaborated on in the next section.

2.4 Types of Corrective Feedback

There are different CF types and various sources for providing them which are classified in a variety of ways. CF can be provided orally and in written form, as such these two are generally the major categories of CF (Sheen, 2010). Each of the oral CF and written CF has differences, and they also comprise subcategories (Karim, 2013). Oral CF usually takes place during the task, while written CF is provided after the task is finished (Sheen, 2010). Oral CF can be further divided into implicit and explicit (Sheen & Ellis, 2011). Implicit oral CF can be provided in the form of recast “when the teacher reformulates part or the whole of the incorrect utterance”, prompts “when the teacher repeats the incorrect utterance or asks for clarification” or in the form of clarification requests where the feedback provider indirectly signals an error by using phrases like 'Pardon' or 'I don't understand' after a student's utterance (Lyster et al., 2013, p. 3). In contrast, explicit oral CF can take the form of explicit correction “when the teacher identifies the incorrect form and gives the correct one”, or elicitation when the teacher “directly elicits a self-correction from the student, often in the form of a Wh-question” (Sheen & Ellis, 2011). Besides oral CF, there is also written CF which is defined as a teacher's written comment on a learner's erroneous structure in a written text (Bitchener & Storch, 2016). As far as the subcategories of written CF is concerned, they will be discussed in the next section (see section 2.7) because they will be elaborated on in detail as they are the focus of this study.

Moreover, when it comes to the question of ‘who should be the source of CF’, again it will be divided into two subcategories which are teacher CF and peer CF (Sato & Lyster, 2012). Karim (2013) declares that although CF provided by the teacher is not the only source, it is the primary form as it is the original source of instruction to the learners. Accordingly, teachers need to have an elevated level of knowledge and the required skills to qualify for this mission as it is not an easy duty (Ellis, 2010a). Despite the importance of teacher CF, peer CF also has a significant value in certain situations especially in crowded classes because the teacher cannot afford to provide enough CF for all the students; however, it still cannot replace the teacher's role (Bitchener & Ferris, 2012). There is a massive body of research about which source of CF is more effective (Mahvelati, 2021), but as their priority is not the focus of this study; thus, they will not be elaborated upon any further. After defining CF and discussing its distinct categories, now moving on to the focus of this study which is Written Corrective Feedback (WCF), the next sections will elaborate

on WCF and its types.

2.4.1 Definition of Written Corrective Feedback and its Scope

The definition of the term WCF has been attempted by many researchers who have tackled it from different perspectives. Irwin (2017) defines WCF as the case when errors are directly or indirectly corrected, admiration is expressed, comments are made, advice is provided, and suggestions are made for students to improve their writing. However, one of the most comprehensive definitions is by Bitchener and Storch (2016) who describe WCF as “a written response to a linguistic error that has been made in the writing of a text by an L2 learner” (p.3). They further indicate its aim as either to give the correct form of the error or to locate the error, its nature, its cause, and how it can be corrected. When it comes to the scope of WCF, there are different perspectives among researchers. For example, Truscott (1996, as stated by Cárcamo, 2020) provides a narrow view of the scope of WCF to only tackle grammatical errors. Bitchener and Storch (2016) step further in stating that although WCF is mainly provided on grammatical errors, it may be provided on non-grammatical errors as well such as punctuation and spelling. Furthermore, Frear (2012) broadens the scope of WCF to comprise CF on all linguistic errors including grammar, lexis, syntax, discourse features and “mechanics (punctuation and capitalization)”, but “it excludes concerns with content and organization” (P. 12). In contrast, Al Jarrah (2016) believes that WCF scope is wider even to include comments on content and organization alongside linguistic errors. He rather believes that the major concern of WCF should be on content and organizational error correction rather than on linguistics errors.

As a result of the different definitions provided above by different scholars and researchers, WCF can be understood differently, but it can include a written comment regarding errors related to grammar, lexis, syntax, discourse features, punctuation, capitalization, content, and organization. As far as the current study is concerned, the chosen scope of the provided CF is only a set of grammatical errors based on the findings of the studies conducted in KRI. According to a study conducted by Mahmood (2016), where he investigated the errors of 30 EFL students at the English language department at the University of Suleimani, the most common error type that Kurdish EFL students make is grammatical errors. Additionally, in another study by Aziz, Ahmed and Salim (2021), the same result confirmed that the most widespread errors made by Kurdish EFL writers are

grammatical errors. They conducted the study at the department of English at both Koya and Salaheddin universities. As such, their suggestion is that the current need of the EFL Kurdish writers requires that teachers concentrate on grammatical errors more thoroughly, especially by providing more WCF.

Having explained the definitions and scope of WCF, now it is time to move to explaining its contribution to acquiring the second language and L2 writing.

2.4.2 The Role of WCF in L2 Development and L2 Writing

L2 development includes all the processes and steps involved in developing a student's L2 knowledge so that the student can use the target language accurately (Bitchener & Storch, 2016). The first stage of this development starts with receiving some L2 input such as WCF which after some time will be transformed into automatized output (Bitchener & Storch, 2016). Despite the controversy over the efficacy of WCF (see section 2.5.), a massive body of research has proved the contribution of WCF in developing learner's L2 and writing accuracy (Chandler, 2003; Ekanayaka & Ellis, 2020; Ferris, 1997; Ferris, 1999; Ferris & Helt, 2000; Sheen, 2007). When students receive WCF, they will be enabled to notice the gap between their level and the required level as their attention will be drawn to the location of the error, its type and correction. Furthermore, Dabboub (2019) states that "WCF helps learners to improve awareness, knowledge, and strategic competence and encourage them to assess their writing, notice possible aspects of weaknesses, and be aware of their performance level" (p. 33). She further adds up that the absence of WCF can make students demotivated, or even anxious which are both two crucial elements in affecting the L2 learning process. Bitchener and Storch (2016) state that the provision of WCF on learner's errors can accord to the characteristics of The Zone of Proximal Development (ZPD) because it can demonstrate the difference between what a learner can produce without assistance (in this case, WCF) and what s/he can achieve with assistance. As such, WCF can be used as an effective scaffolding technique in assisting learners to engage with the form of the produced L2 writing.

By pushing the learner to attend the form, WCF can be regarded as a focus-on-form method where learners' attention is forwarded towards the written output (Ellis, 2005). With that being stated, the focus-on-form approach to L2 teaching is proved effective and useful

in facilitating learners' accuracy and fluency (Williams, 1998). Furthermore, WCF can function as a proper mean for following contextualized grammar teaching because otherwise, the learners will be unable to transfer the isolated learned grammatical forms to be used in real and meaningful contexts (Dabboub, 2019).

Moreover, WCF can facilitate L2 development in that it prepares the foreground for interaction as the role of interaction is long being discussed and valued (Long, 1996). WCF assists the learners and the feedback provider (in most cases the teacher) to interact about the writing output and the produced language by the learner. When the teacher evaluates the learners' writing and provides feedback then the learners can review the writing based on that evaluation and maybe provide a revised text, these all well fit into the Interaction Hypothesis proposed by Long (1996). Face-to-face interactions and communication are said to promote the development of language proficiency according to the Interaction hypothesis of second-language acquisition. It focuses mainly on the role of inputs, interactions and outputs in second language development (Johnson & Johnson, 1998). In addition to the roles outlined above, there are several other roles of WCF that have been the subject of a long and heated debate that has covered a vast amount of research on WCF. They will, therefore, be elaborated on in the following sections (see sections 2.5 and 2.5.1).

2.5 The Debate on the Efficacy of WCF

There has been a heated debate about the effectiveness of WCF in facilitating L2 learning and L2 writing accuracy. Although several researchers have questioned the potential usefulness of WCF (Kepner, 1991; Lalande, 1982; Semke, 1984;), this debate mainly started with Truscott's review article (1996) titled "The Case against Grammar Correction in L2 Writing Classes". Truscott (1996) argues that there are some issues with claiming error correction (EC) efficacy in L2 writing classes. According to him, research evidence indicates that EC is ineffective, which makes sense given the natural order of L2 acquisition and interlanguage development. Moreover, he even argues that EC has significant harmful effects as it causes stress to the students and leads to demotivation in learning L2. Therefore, he concludes the article by stating that "grammar correction has no place in writing courses and should be abandoned" (p.328). Since then, ample amount of research has been conducted to investigate the role of WCF in L2 learning and L2 writing accuracy

and to refute Truscott's claim (Abbas & Tawfeeq, 2018b; Bitchener, 2008; Boggs, 2019; Chandler, 2003; Ekanayaka & Ellis, 2020; Ellis, 2009; Ellis et al., 2008; Ferris, 1997; 1999; Frear, 2012; Karim & Nassaji, 2019; Kurzer, 2018; Mao & Lee, 2020; Polio et al., 1998; Poorebrahim, 2017; Shintani & Ellis, 2015; Shintani & Ellis, 2013; Shintani et al., 2014; Soltanpour & Valizadeh, 2018; Van Beuningen, 2011; Van Beuningen et al., 2012; Zhang, 2020)

Nevertheless, the most comprehensive and straightforward response to Truscott's article is "The Case for Grammar Correction in L2 Writing Classes: A Response to Truscott (1996)" written by Ferris (1999). Ferris in her rebuttal believes that Truscott rushes to conclusions about the effectiveness of EC; thus, she adds that "let us not rely on inadequate evidence to make important pedagogical decisions" (p. 10). She states that Truscott's claim has two critical issues which are the definition of error correction and the support utilized to prove his claim. Concerning the first flaw which is the definition of error correction, Truscott (1996) defines it as the "correction of grammatical errors for the purpose of improving a student's ability to write accurately" (p.329). Ferris believes that this definition of error correction is vague and does not specify exactly what is error correction and which type of error correction is not effective. She adds further that we all "agree that poorly done error correction will not help student writers and may even mislead them" (1999, p.4). She also argues that if a proper error correction type is applied which is "selective, prioritized, and clear" it can be effective in assisting learners to improve (1999, p.4). Accordingly, she asserts that for discussing whether grammar correction is effective or not we should specify which type of error we are reviewing.

When it comes to the second critique by Ferris (1999) which is related to the support from literature, Truscott believes that the research evidence does not support the provision of error correction, while Ferris argues that Truscott's support for this argument lacks validity. Ferris finds the support given by Truscott to have the following issues: First, "the subjects in the various studies are not comparable" because it entails different subjects, and they are from different contexts. Second, "the research paradigms and teaching strategies vary widely across the studies" as the mechanics for giving feedback and the period for treatment is not long enough thus it causes methodology problems. Finally, Truscott overstates those studies which support his view while neglecting those which prove the efficacy of error correction (Ferris, 1999, p.5).

Moreover, Truscott (1996) claims that there are two key issues with the provision of EC which he names theoretical and practical issues. Concerning the theoretical issues, he believes that due to the order of acquisition theory, learners cannot benefit from the correction of an item they receive if still, they are not in the right order of acquiring this item. He states that “the acquisition of grammatical structure is a gradual process, not a sudden discovery as the intuitive view of correction would imply” (1996, p.342). Despite Ferris’s acknowledgment of this issue about the order of acquisition of L2 structures, she comments that this does not mean that it is not treatable, and we simply give up without assisting and scaffolding our learners. She believes that this can be managed by informing the learners about the importance of self-editing to motivate them, training them on how to identify their errors and to self-correct themselves, giving them explicit teaching about such structures and providing them with indirect feedback instead of direct feedback. When it comes to idiosyncratic errors (i.e., errors that cannot be corrected by following specific rules or structures) in some structures, Ferris (1999) also finds it problematic to be acquired through correction. However, she still thinks there is a solution to this as well which can be achieved by a change in the strategy such as “a combination of strategy training and direct correction” (1999, p.6).

As far as the practical aspects of error correction is concerned, Truscott connects them to the issues relevant to students and teachers. Firstly, he believes that teachers are not qualified enough to deal with errors because they are not able to notice if an error has been made. Even if they are able to detect the error, they are still not competent enough to give a good explanation while correcting the error. He further argues that even if we suppose the teachers are qualified to correct the errors, they still cannot manage to perform it as it is time-consuming and teachers are already burdened and busy with extra duties (Truscott, 1996, p.350). On the other hand, Ferris (1999) counterargues that this is still not an unsolvable issue because teachers already need preparation and training. Thus, if teachers are well-trained, they will be able to deal with these concerns raised by Truscott. She goes further to comment that teachers also need to be prioritizing and selective in their feedback so as to keep up with time and to be far from burnout. Notwithstanding, Truscott still believes that even if all of the above issues are resolved, still students are not able to benefit from the provided feedback because either they do not understand the explanations, or even if they do so, they will still not absorb it and forget the new knowledge quickly. Again, Ferris

regards this as invalid reasoning because, in her view, this can also be managed if we take into consideration “the first language background of the learners, their language proficiency, and their prior experience with English grammar instruction” (1999, p. 7) and the points mentioned above. Ferris ends her response article by stating that we should continue with correcting our students’ errors alongside the positive points mentioned earlier. Several researchers investigated students’ and teachers’ perceptions in favouring the provision of feedback and correction (see section 2.6).

Moreover, and above all, in 2008, precisely 12 years after his article in 1996, Truscott conducted a study with Hsu to investigate the efficacy of learners’ revision after their errors were corrected. At the beginning of the article, he tries to defend his old view by stating that revision is not related to the efficacy of error correction. However, this argument is not possible because once a researcher assesses the effectiveness of revision after the provided feedback, this already implies that the researcher has accepted the validity of error correction in the first place. In addition to that, in the conclusion of the article (Truscott & Hsu, 2008, p. 299), it is clearly stated that “our findings confirm once again that correction does help students reduce their errors on the writing on which they receive the corrections, and that the effect is substantial”.

As it was previously indicated at the beginning of this section, a considerable amount of research has been conducted to test and prove the efficacy of WCF. The following subsection (2.5.1) refers to some studies which have assessed the effectiveness of WCF in general. Moreover, there are other studies that have dealt with WCF more specifically in terms of types (direct vs. indirect or focused vs. unfocused) and when revision is required. These all will be elaborated in their specified forthcoming sections (section 2.7.1, 2.7.2 & 2.9).

2.5.1 Empirical Studies About the Efficacy of WCF

As it was stated earlier, there are plenty of studies proving the efficacy of WCF by conducting experiments in various contexts. To start with, Chandler (2003) conducted research in the USA at the College of New England Conservatory of Music and Simmons. Her research is comprised of two studies. Her first study aims to determine whether correcting students’ errors improves accuracy. In her second study, she also researches

how and what type of feedback should be provided, but this topic will not be discussed in this section because it will be addressed under WCF types (see section 2.7). Concerning her first study, she utilized an experimental design to test a total of 31 students who are from the East Asia (16 students in the control group and 15 students in the treatment group). The students in both groups were asked to write twenty-five pages of autobiographies over the semester. The control group was not required to correct their errors while the treatment group's errors were required to be corrected throughout the semester. The results of her first study illustrate that there is a significant difference between both groups in that the treatment group's accuracy increased. Therefore, she concludes by stating that this result refutes "the assertion that having students correct errors is ineffective" (2003, p. 279).

In a similar vein, Bitchener (2008) conducted a study in two private schools in Auckland, New Zealand to evaluate 75 intermediate international ESL students on the feedback they receive. He employed a pre-test, an immediate post-test and a delayed post-test. The treatment group received corrective feedback while the control group received no feedback over the period of two months. The aim was to examine if there is a difference between the groups in the use of two functional uses of the English article system ("a" and "the"). The results revealed that WCF has a significant effect and the accuracy of the treatment group improved in the use of these two articles compared to the control group.

Furthermore, in another study carried out by Zarei and Rahnama (2013), the efficacy of WCF was measured. The study is conducted at three different universities in Iran. The participants were 164 BA students in their third and fourth semesters for a period of twelve sessions (whole semester). For the purpose of data collection, an experimental study was employed, and the students were divided into the treatment group (n=85) who received WCF on their lexical and grammatical errors, and the control group (n=79) who received no WCF. The results once again demonstrated that WCF has verifying effects on improving learners' lexical and grammatical accuracy. Moreover, another support study will be demonstrated as it is conducted in the context of Iraqi Kurdistan region to closely relate it to the current study. The study was conducted by Abbas and Tawfeeq (2018b) at two public universities (Sulaimani University and Charmo University) in the Iraqi Kurdistan region. The aim of the study was to investigate the impact of WCF on the learners' linguistic accuracy. The researchers used an experimental design for the purpose of data collection. In KRI, this is the only study that uses an experimental design to investigate WCF's effectiveness. The

participants were 105 third-year undergraduate EFL students from both universities divided into treatment and control groups. The treatment group received comprehensive WCF targeting grammatical, lexical, and mechanical (spelling and punctuation) errors over the period of 8 weeks and wrote four essays. The control group underwent the same process but without receiving any WCF. The results yielded proof of the efficacy of WCF in improving EFL learners' linguistic accuracy over time. As it was stated at the beginning of this section, there is a substantial body of empirical research that has been conducted in different contexts, all of which have shown that WCF has a positive impact, supporting its provision, some of them were presented above and there are many others (e.g., in Iran by Khanlarzadeh & Nemati, 2016; in USA by Kurzer, 2018; in Egypt by Sabbahi, 2017), but they will not be elaborated upon in order to avoid making it too long for the reader.

In addition to discussing WCF's efficacy in light of the literature, it is important to explore the distinct types of WCF provided by the teacher, as they may have different impacts and roles in improving L2 students' writing accuracy (Ellis, 2009; Sheen et al., 2009) (see section 2.6 below).

2.6 Types of Written Corrective Feedback

Despite the fact that there are several forms of WCF, they are generally divided into direct, indirect, focused, and unfocused WCF (Bitchener & Knoch, 2015) which are discussed in the following sections.

2.6.1 Direct WCF Versus Indirect WCF

Direct feedback (also called overt or explicit feedback) is defined by Ellis (2009) as the case when “the teacher provides the student with the correct form” (p.99). Direct feedback can take different forms such as “crossing out an unnecessary word, phrase, or morpheme, inserting a missing word or morpheme, and writing the correct form above or near to the erroneous form” (Ellis, 2009, p.99). In contrast, indirect WCF (also called covert or implicit feedback) is to indicate that an error has been made in any way but without providing any explicit correction (Ferris, 2003). It can be provided in three ways: “underlining or circling the error; recording in the margin the number of errors in a given line; or using a code to show where the error has occurred and what type of error it is” (Bitchener & Knoch, 2009,

p.323).

As stated earlier, there are different views among researchers about the most effective WCF type as there are different conclusions drawn from the conducted studies. Direct WCF is more beneficial for those students who have a low proficiency level because they might not know the correct form, and the direct WCF provides them with explicit guidance about the required correct form of the language (Ellis, 2009). However, since the learners are provided with a straightforward correction and the correct version of the language, it needs little amount of processing as such it does not contribute to long-term learning (Ellis, 2009). While in the indirect WCF, since the students are required to ponder about the correct form and work on it is more demanding and requires deeper processing. Additionally, it has been stated that indirect WCF “caters to guided learning and problem solving, it also encourages students to reflect about linguistic forms” as a result, it can lead to long-term learning (Ellis, 2009, p.100). According to Spivey (2014), direct WCF is more helpful as it is very straightforward and leaves no room for confusion or debate, while Lefkowitz (1994) believes that indirect WCF is better since it makes the students be more active. Furthermore, according to Ferris (2006, as cited in Al Shahrani, 2013), direct WCF is more helpful for errors that are “untreatable” i.e., errors where students might not be able to correct themselves because “there are no specific rules”, while indirect WCF is beneficial for “treatable errors”; “errors that students may be able to self-correct, and which have specific rules” (p.9).

Moreover, Najmaddin (2010) examined the effect of direct and indirect CF on 31 first-year students at Koya University Iraq through questionnaires and interviews. The results showed that direct CF is more effective specifically for low-level students. In the study carried out by Chandler (2003) in the USA where there are ESL music students at the college of New England Conservatory of Music and Simmons, the efficacy of both direct and indirect WCF is tested in the second part. The second part is experimental research that attempted to determine the best method of error correction. The experiment was conducted on 36 East Asian undergraduate students who were divided into two groups. The students in the first group were provided with direct correction while the other group received indirect feedback. She concludes the study by stating that the results suggest that the best method “for producing precise revisions” is direct feedback; it is also preferred by students and professors because it is the quickest and most convenient method” (2003, p. 267).

In a similar manner, Karim (2013) conducted a study in Canada to examine the comparative efficiency of various feedback categories on learners' writing accuracy for 6 weeks to participate in seven sessions. He also utilized experimental design to assess 53 intermediate English as a Second Language learners studying at two ESL schools in Canada. He divided the participants into three groups (direct CF, indirect CF and no CF group). The findings revealed that although the two CF groups surpassed the no CF group, the direct CF group demonstrated substantial improvement in improving grammatical accuracy in new writing pieces.

Conversely, in a study conducted in Karaj, Iran by Eslami (2014), for which the researcher examined 60 low intermediate EFL students, a different result was achieved. The participants were divided into two groups (one group received direct CF while the other group received indirect CF) where they were required to produce three different pieces of writing (pre-test, immediate post-test, and delayed post-test). The results showed that the indirect CF group exceeded the direct CF group. Similarly, Hosseiny (2014) conducted a study in Iran to evaluate 60 pre-intermediate students in an institution in Ardabil. She divided the participants into three groups exactly like in the previous study. Although her study illustrated no significant difference between the two feedback types, still indirect CF was more preferred because "indirect feedback always encourages the learner to take part in the process of repair, which puts him or her in the appropriate framework to at least acknowledge the suggested solution and, therefore, to notice it" (Hosseiny, p. 672).

In the meantime, there are other experimental studies whose results demonstrate that there are no significant differences between learners in the indirect CF group and direct CF group in improving their writing accuracy although both types were proven to be effective compared to non-feedback groups (Bitchener & Storch, 2016; Choi, 2013).

Furthermore, there is another empirical research conducted by Van Beuningen et al., (2012) in the Netherlands showed that these two types of CF each are effective for different purposes. The researchers in an experimental study investigated the performance of 268 participants after receiving both types of CF in Dutch high schools over 5 weeks. The results indicated that both types assisted students to enhance their accuracy, but the direct CF was more efficient for improving grammatical errors while indirect CF was more helpful for improving non-grammatical accuracy. Nevertheless, Ferris (2003), in her deep investigation of her book regarding the response mechanism of instructors to the learners' writings, states

that “Most researchers agree that indirect feedback has more potential than direct feedback for long-term student improvement because of increased student engagement and attention to forms and problems” (pp. 51,52).

Based on the aforementioned studies and views of the researchers, indirect WCF can better contribute to long-term learning. Since one of the objectives of the present research is to investigate if WCF plus revision can have long-term effects, as such the indirect type of WCF will be provided to the learners in the study.

2.6.2 Focused WCF Versus Unfocused WCF

Concerning the focus of the WCF, it can be divided into focused and unfocused WCF. Sheen, Wright and Moldawa (2009) describe unfocused WCF (also called comprehensive WCF) as involving the correction of all the errors, or a wide variety of errors made in the students’ writing by the teacher. Ellis et al., (2008) regard this type as the traditional approach and view it as “-extensive because it treats multiple errors” (p.356). On the other hand, Focused WCF (also called selective WCF) emphasizes a specific type of error or errors to be targeted while neglecting the rest (Ellis, et al, 2008).

There is a debate about how much focus the teacher gives to the types of errors the students make in their writing, whether the instructor corrects all, part, or a single type of error (Ellis et al, 2008; Sheen et al, 2009). Ellis et al., (2008) in their study about the impact of focused and unfocused feedback stated that:

There are solid theoretical reasons for believing that focused CF will be more effective than unfocused CF. Learners are more likely to attend to corrections directed at a single (or a limited number of) error type(s) and more likely to develop a clearer understanding of the nature of the error and the correction needed. (p.356)

Moreover, Bitchener (2008, as cited in Dabboub, 2019) believes that when students are required to respond to a large amount of linguistic aspects, as L2 learners have deficient processing capability, this may cause “cognitive overload” and hinder the processing of the feedback. On the contrary, Anderson (2010) believes that focused CF might not be practical for content teachers who still aim to comment on linguistic errors as well, it will also confuse learners to see a part of their errors has been corrected and others have not.

However, Sheen (2007, as cited in Frear, 2012) claims that focused CF decreases the “attentional strain” on the learners. Frear further keeps on to state that “when focused CF is combined with direct CF, it should increase the likelihood of noticing errors, and when it is combined with indirect CF, it could enhance the chances for modified output” (2012, p. 34).

To sum up, although there are different views about which type of WCF (focused or unfocused) to be provided, but most of the aforementioned studies have favoured the focused WCF over unfocused WCF as it does not overload the learner and it better leads to processing the feedback which in return contributes learning. Based on these arguments the current study has investigated the use of focused WCF.

Having discussed the efficiency of WCF and the distinct types of WCF in the light of the available literature, now, it is of critical need to review the insights of the learners and instructors towards the importance of WCF and the challenges and problems that they face during the implementation of WCF.

2.7 Teacher’s and Students’ Perception Towards WCF

Despite teachers’ and learners’ mainly positive attitudes toward WCF, they have different preferences in terms of the types and mechanisms of WCF. (Chandler, 2003; Galaly, 2017; Lee, 2008; Montgomery & Baker, 2007). In the study conducted by Montgomery and Baker (2007) in a University in USA, teachers’ and students’ perceptions were tested via questionnaire. The study found that students prefer to have a lot of comments on their paper because this makes them feel more engaged in the process of learning. Additionally, Hama and Ismael (2018), in a study conducted at Suleimani university, aimed at discovering the perceptions of the university learners towards the importance of providing WCF. In the study, 80 third-year students at the college of basic education filled out a questionnaire and it was found that most of the participants regard WCF provision as a vital means for improving grammatical aspect, function, and style of writing. In a similar vein, Galaly (2017) conducted a study in the KRI high schools to investigate instructors’ and learners’ perceptions towards the benefits of WCF in improving writing. The study findings demonstrated a positive stance by both instructors and learners towards providing WCF because they thought it facilitates L2 writing development. Moreover, a positive relation was

found between teachers' provided WCF and students' motivation (Galaly, 2017).

However, according to the study conducted at a KRI university by Mahmood (2019), students favoured to have further feedback on linguistic errors rather than on the content. Similarly, in the study by Amrhein and Nassaji (2010, as cited in Dabboub, 2019), it was found that learners favoured to have feedback on errors related to grammar and mechanics of writing (punctuation and spelling) while teachers believed it is necessary to provide feedback on all features of writing (such as grammar, punctuation, spelling and content). Contrariwise, there are learners who would like to receive feedback on the content rather than on the grammatical aspects because this will make them be more creative in producing more meaningful texts rather than pondering on the grammatical errors (Chiang, 2004).

Additionally, students have different views about the provided WCF type (Chandler, 2003). In her study investigating ESL learners' and teachers' views towards distinct types of WCF, Chandler (2003) found that half of the learners favoured to have direct WCF as it is less troublesome to find and correct their errors which was the case for some teachers as well since less time is required to provide the feedback. On the contrary, she also found that the other half of the students liked to receive indirect WCF because they believe they can learn better by only underlining the error rather than receiving the correct form. Similarly, some teachers also preferred the underlining method of WCF because it is even less time-consuming than direct correction (Chandler, 2003). Concerning the difficulties learners and teachers face throughout the process of receiving and providing WCF, students have mainly reported that they cannot understand the codes on their writing tasks, the instructors' handwriting is difficult to read, or the learner fail to understand the teachers' point about the error (Chiang, 2004). As far as the teachers are concerned, they have reported that it is time-consuming (Ferris, 1999) and that some students neglect the feedback or even fail to attend to the error (Truscott, 1996).

To sum up, teachers and students have different opinions with regard to the mechanism of WCF provision, and they both face challenges and difficulties in the application of this process. This unpredictable attitude of students can be related back to their different proficiency level, education background and their learning target (Dabboub, 2019). Further, Ferris (2006) and Bitchener et al., (2005) have shown that the type of error that is corrected has a major impact on students' attitudes and the effectiveness of WCF,

which is why it is so critical to review the literature about the distinct types of errors that are corrected (see section 2.8 below).

2.8 Which Errors to Correct?

While correcting learners' errors, teachers should know how to treat the errors, which one to approach, and which error should receive attention. The major schemes of the error types in the literature are local vs. global and treatable vs. untreatable errors (Bitchener & Ferris, 2012; Tran, 2013). Ferris (2003) tackles the types of error to be addressed as such she differentiates between treatable and untreatable errors. According to her, untreatable errors are idiosyncratic errors that are not rule-governed such as lexical errors, collocations and any other "idiosyncratic errors" while treatable errors are rule-governed errors such as regular past tense, article usage, etc. (p.51).

The other distinction between local and global errors as described by Tran (2013) is that local errors are the ones that do not obstruct the comprehension of the text, while global errors are errors that hamper the understanding of the text. Another criterion for selecting errors is the frequency of the errors where the most frequent ones receive the most attention (Bitchener & Ferris, 2012). Therefore, the emphasis of the feedback correction should be more on errors that are global and treatable (Bitchener & Ferris, 2012). As such, it can be noticed that most of the feedback studies focus on the English article system because it is categorized under treatable errors (Choi, 2013; Shintani & Ellis, 2013).

In light of this, this paper addresses how to correct errors that are both global (i.e., hinder communication) and treatable (i.e., rule-governed for example, regular past tense). Ferris (2003) explains that, if the error categories are not selected carefully, feedback might not result in learning. In this instance, the effectiveness of the WCF cannot be questioned, rather, it can be attributed to the teacher's wrong choice.

After discussing the efficacy of WCF, its scope, its types, the mechanisms for providing it and which errors to target, an important concern remains to be addressed. The concern is that students may not be paying attention to the provided feedback, as such the WCF might go unnoticed, and teachers' efforts may be in vain. Therefore, the next section will turn to the main focus of the study, which is the role that revision might play in making WCF more effective.

2.9 The Mediating Role of Asking Learners to Revise Their Writing After Receiving WCF

The role of revision after receiving WCF has been addressed by a few researchers who have investigated its possible impact on making WCF be more effective (Chandler, 2003; Ekanayaka & Ellis, 2020; Ferris, 1997; Frear, 2012; Li, 2017; Polio et al, 1998; Shintani et al, 2014; Soltanpour & Valizadeh, 2018; Truscott & Hsu, 2008). According to Ellis (2009), revision can be viewed as part of WCF where students might and might not be requested to modify their texts after they received feedback. However, it is possible for learners to ignore corrections and their shortcomings if they are not required to respond to them (Ellis, 2009). Therefore, it becomes necessary to examine the potential impact of asking learners to revise the corrected text they have received. According to Ellis (2009, as cited in Li, 2017), WCF cannot have the utmost effect on accuracy if the learners are not required to respond to it. Also, Williams (2012, as cited in Soltanpour & Valizadeh, 2018) argues that “during revision, learners are able to access their explicit L2 knowledge and notice the gap between it and their first draft production” (p. 1). As it was mentioned earlier in section 2.3, the benefits of CF and revision are made clearer when compared to the five steps of the micro cognitive process of input processing proposed by Gass (1997). The stages are noticing the input, understanding it, turning the input into intake, internalization of the learned structure through practicing, and modified output (uptake) (Gass, 1997). The first three stages of the process were described in section 2.3 and were associated with the CF role, and in this section, the last two stages will be described which are achieved through asking learners to revise. According to Ellis and Ekanayaka (2020), when learners are required to revise, they are practicing the correction and use the learned structure repeatedly. This will allow the internalization and automatization of the learned structure. Internalization, According to Metwalli (2020), internalization “is the process of making something internal, with more specific meanings in various fields” (p.1). Automatization is when the learner automatically produces target-like structures without having to think about it (Hummel, 2014). In addition to this, Ellis (2010b) states that revision requirement forces the students to produce output (the revised version) which according to Swain’s comprehensible output hypothesis (1993), will be an additive source for L2 writing learning. This is due to the fact that Swain believes only attending the input (WCF in this case) is not enough for improving grammatical knowledge and L2 competency, it is also necessary to notice the output (the revised version

in this case).

Furthermore, Guenette (2007, as cited in Ellis, 2009) believes that “students have to notice the feedback and be given ample opportunities to apply the corrections” (p. 106). Additionally, Frear (2012, p.16) argues for different benefits of revision depending on the type of provided feedback where he states that WCF plus revision “can lead to opportunities to notice the correction (direct CF) or it can lead to chances for pushed output (indirect CF)”. In contrary to the above-mentioned studies, Truscott and Hsu (2008), in their research about the role of revision in reducing learners’ errors while writing their assignments, found out that asking students to revise is not a predictor of learning. As such, Bitchener and Ferris (2012) state that the biggest challenge they have faced during their review of the WCF studies is whether demanding students to revise their writing following CF is useful in improving accuracy.

As stated earlier, the findings about the mediating role of revision have been inconclusive. There are studies that have proven its positive impact on error reduction (e.g., Chandler 2003; Ekanayaka & Ellis, 2020; Ferris, 1997). Ferris (1997) conducted a study at a large public university in California to test the writings of 47 advanced ESL students. She examined teacher comments on 110 drafts then she compared them to the revised version to observe the role of revision. She found that revision has increasingly assisted students to improve. Similarly, Chandler (2003) conducted a study in the USA where she had two groups and each group included 31 ESL learners (control group received CF but no revision was required while the treatment group was requested to revise their writings). Her results demonstrated that the treatment group surpassed the control group in terms of accuracy. In a similar design, Ekanayaka and Ellis (2020) studied ninety-one students in Sri Lanka where they were divided into three groups (WCF plus revision; WCF plus peer feedback; no WCF) to write three tasks over the period of four weeks. The results showed that the two groups that received WCF improved their accuracy as compared to the no-CF group. They also found that the revision group achieved maximum gains in terms of accuracy improvement.

On the other hand, Truscott and Hsu (2008) found opposite results for the mediating role of revision in their study. The study was conducted at a public university in Taiwan for which 47 ESL students were divided into two groups (those who got WCF plus revision and those who received WCF without revision). They concluded that “no relation was found

between success on the revision task and learning as measured by performance on a new writing task” (p.299).

Besides, there are studies that have found that although revision adds on the effect of WCF, it might not be at a level to have practical implications (i.e., improvement is minimal and does not extend to new pieces of writing, as such, it has a weak reason to be added to the curriculum) (e.g., Polio et al, 1998; Poorebrahim, 2017). Polio et al (1998) conducted a study at Michigan State University to test 65 ESL students for a period of 7 weeks. They concluded the study by stating that although there is an interesting improvement in the students’ accuracy, the improvement is too small to have practical implications. Similarly, Poorebrahim (2017) conducted a study in Iran to examine the effect of revision on 20 EFL students at a general English course at a private English school. The learners were divided into two groups where both groups received indirect WCF (indication for group one and indication plus location for group two) and were required to revise their text. Indication type is when the sentence that contains the error is marked without marking the exact erroneous word while indication plus location type locates the exact word. The results showed that although the rate of students’ errors had reduced, “that error reduction in revision stage cannot be considered as learning” (p.184) because the difference between the two groups was not significant, it was rather a slight improvement in scores.

There are other studies that have found that revision can have the utmost effects with a specific type of WCF. Frear (2012) conducted a study in China at the university level. 106 ESL students participated in the seven-week study where they were divided into five groups (Focused Direct CF, Unfocused Direct CF, Focused Indirect CF, Unfocused Indirect CF, no CF). All the treatment groups were required to revise their writing. The results indicated that all the feedback and revision groups performed better than the no CF group. Also, the focused groups in both the indirect and direct CF outperformed the other groups of unfocused CF.

On the other hand, a study conducted by Shintani et al (2014) which followed the same research design as Frear (2012), revealed that Direct CF is the most effective type of CF once the revision is required. They conducted the study in Japan with the participation of 214 university students from seven classes. The researchers employed an experimental study where the participants were divided into five groups (direct CF, Metalinguistic CF,

direct CF plus revision, Metalinguistic CF plus revision, no CF) in five sessions over five weeks. The aim was to evaluate students' accuracy in the use of two grammatical structures: indefinite article and hypothetical conditional. They found that feedback only helped in improving hypothetical conditional but not with the indefinite articles. They also found that all the revision groups outperformed the non-revision groups although the direct CF plus revision achieved the best gains.

2.10 Research Gaps

After a thorough review of the available literature, the researcher found out that there are some research gaps due to flaws in the design and methods of the conducted studies. These research gaps will be approached in separation in terms of context (contexts outside Kurdistan Region of Iraq (KRI) and inside the KRI).

Starting with the studies outside the context of Iraqi Kurdistan Region, there are some research gaps and methodological flaws in these studies. For example, the studies conducted by Polio et al (1998), Chandler (2003) and Poorebrahim (2017) who investigated the add-on effect of revision plus WCF, lack a control group. As a result, it is difficult to reach reliable conclusions about the effectiveness of WCF on L2 and L2 writing accuracy without having a control group, i.e., an experiment (Ekanayaka & Ellis, 2020). Furthermore, there are studies that have utilized a control group for a short-term "one-shot" treatment (e.g., Ferris, 1997) while this practice needs to be investigated over a period of time to see whether or not the effects transfer to new pieces of writing. As such, the current study attempts to fill this gap by studying the effect of WCF plus revision across five writing tasks within 14 weeks, leaving a two-month interval between the immediate posttest and delayed post-test in order to accurately check if the effect is long-term and applies to new writing pieces.

Additionally, the current study will be the first attempt to explore the effectiveness of focused indirect WCF plus revision because Ekanayaka and Ellis (2020) and Shintani et al., (2014) examined focused direct WCF plus revision, also, Soltanpour and Valizadeh (2018) studied comprehensive direct WCF plus revision, while according to the most of previously cited literature, indirect feedback seems to be more effective (Ellis, 2009; Eslami, 2014; Ferris, 2003; Frear, 2012; Hosseiny, 2014). The reason is this type of feedback leads to

pushed output (Frear, 2012), better student engagement (Ferris, 2003) and long-term learning (Ellis, 2009).

As far as the studies inside the context of KRI are concerned, the researcher was able to locate seven studies about the provision of WCF (i.e., Abbas & Tawfeeq, 2018a; Abbas & Tawfeeq, 2018b; Chaqmaqchee, 2015; Galaly, 2017; Hama & Ismael, 2018; Mahmood, 2019; Najmaddin, 2010). First of all, none of these studies, other than Abbas and Tawfeeq (2018b), have studied the mediating role of revision, they have rather approached the role of CF in general. As far as Abbas and Tawfeeq (2018b) is concerned, although they made attempts to investigate the effect of WCF followed by revision, they did not directly address the influence of revision in enhancing grammatical accuracy of L2 students writing. Secondly, most of these studies (e.g., Chaqmaqchee, 2015; Galaly, 2017; Hama & Ismael, 2018; Mahmood, 2019; Najmaddin, 2010) have sought to examine the impact of WCF solely via learners' and teachers' perception through questionnaires or interviews. While, according to Bitchener and Ferris (2012,) "in order to test whether written CF assists L2 learning, it is necessary to study this practice over time via the means of pre-test, post-test and delayed post-test" (p.51). Therefore, it is difficult to arrive at reliable conclusions about the effectiveness of WCF on L2 and L2 writing accuracy without having a control group i.e., an experimental study (Ekanayaka & Ellis, 2020). Although the two studies conducted by Abbas and Tawfeeq (2018a, 2018b) have used experimental design to examine the role and effect of WCF in improving L2 writing accuracy, as stated earlier, they have not directly approached the add-on effect of revision after the provision of WCF. On that account, to the best knowledge of the researcher, the current study is the first attempt in the context of Iraqi Kurdistan Region to directly examine whether asking students to revise their writings after receiving WCF is effective and adds to the effect of WCF in improving learners' L2 writing accuracy.

Another gap is that the current study will be the first attempt to examine if the impact of WCF plus revision can have more impact on reducing one particular grammatical error type as compared to other error types. Most of the previous revision studies have studied if there will be impact on reducing one error type such as errors in using the English article system alone (e.g., Shintani et al, 2014) or verb forms (e.g., Frear, 2012), while the current attempt will compare the effect of WCF with the add-on of revision on the English article system, subject-verb agreement, verb form, and prepositions of time.

Chapter 3: Methodology

This thesis explores whether revision can contribute to improving EFL learners' grammatical accuracy after receiving the teacher's WCF. Therefore, four questions arise: What is the effect of Indirect Corrective Feedback (ICF) with revision on the grammatical accuracy of L2 students' writing? What is the long-term effect of ICF with revision on the improvement of L2 students' grammatical accuracy? How does revision affect different grammatical features of L2 students' writing? What is the perception of teachers towards the process and effect of revision on students' writing? As such, in the following sections, the researcher describes the design, study procedure, participants, data collection, scoring rubric, and finally, the method for analysing the data so as to provide accurate responses to the posed questions.

3.1 Study Design

To illustrate the paradigm perspective, the researcher utilized mixed-method design following Dornyei's paradigm stance that a mixed method can "offer additional benefits for the understanding of the phenomenon in question" because the quantitative method offers "elaborated technical apparatus" and the qualitative method provides much deeper and richer data (2007, p.47). Therefore, the underpinning paradigm for the quantitative part is post-positivism while the qualitative part paradigm is interpretivism. According to Corebetta (2003), post-positivism asserts that "social reality exists outside the individual" and "social reality is objectively understandable" (p.15). He further states that this paradigm's methodologies and techniques are highly influenced by the classical empiricist approach to natural science, which employs the experimental method of inductive procedures. Its technique is based on manipulation and control of the variables involved, as well as the observer's detachment from what is observed (Corebetta, 2003, p.16).

As a result, to answer research questions, 1,2, and 3, the researcher employed a quasi-experimental method based on the post-positivist paradigm to determine the impact of revision following a teacher's WCF on the L2 learners' grammatical accuracy in the context of Kurdistan. In the quasi-experimental phase, as in a true experimental study, there were two groups: the treatment group, which got the treatment (revision), and the control group, which provided a basis for comparison; the only difference was that unlike experimental research, random assignment was not used to establish the comparison

(Dunford, 1990). In other words, there were already two groups of sophomores, and forming new groups was not feasible. (Dunford, 1990). However, the fact that the study took place in an actual classroom with real class groups eliminated any concerns about lowered external validity (as in real experiments) (Dornyei, 2007). Finally, after 7 sessions, in order to evaluate the effect of the treatment, the accuracy of the pre-tests and post-tests of the two groups was compared.

Moreover, the qualitative phase implemented an interpretivism paradigm that is “emphatic interaction between the researcher and the object of the study” where the reality is interpreted after it is observed (Corebetta, 2003, p.24). Its research techniques are qualitative and subjective (Goldkuhl, 2012). As such, alongside the quasi-experimental study, the researcher also in an exploratory framework of research conducted semi-structured interviews with the teacher of that particular class where the quasi-experiment was applied. To this aim, multi-session interviews with the teacher were conducted to explore the teachers’ perceptions of the practice of revision requirements after the WCF was given. Finally, thematic analysis was utilized to analyse the transcripts of the three session interviews.

3.2 Study Procedures

First of all, the researcher visited the University, College of Languages, Department of English Language to obtain their approval to have their sophomore students and their teacher participate in the research. The class instructor then assigned group A of second-year students as the treatment group and group B as the control group. Following that, the researcher asked the teacher and the learners to participate in the research at their discretion. It was explicitly stated to them that their option to partake or not take part in the study would have no ramifications and would not affect their grades.

The data were collected for the duration of 14 weeks in seven sessions (the students had 7 classes with the instructor in the duration of 14 weeks because the class was once a week and they had 8 weeks intervals between 6th and 7th session) (see table 3.1 presented below). Each session lasted two hours and each group had only one session during the week. After obtaining approval from the department and consent from teachers and students (see Appendix 1 & Appendix 2), in the same week (session 1), all students in both groups completed background questionnaires (see Appendix 3). Moreover, in the same

week, a pilot study was conducted to examine the validity of the quasi-experimental design. A written task was given to 11 students in the treatment group in the pilot study. The teacher provided indirect coded feedback on four grammar errors (article system, subject-verb agreement, verb form, and prepositions of time). The reason for choosing these four grammatical categories was that the three writing teachers in the department reported that these were the most misused grammatical categories among writing students. Following the completion of the assignment in the pilot study, it was found that no students misused the preposition of time, so it was removed from the study. Following the pilot study, the actual study began.

In the following week (session 2), after completing the background questionnaire, all the students in both groups took the pre-test as it is detailed below in section 3.5.1. They were given 45 minutes to write the first assignment inside the classroom which acted as the pre-test. In the following three weeks (session 3,4, and 5), students in the treatment group were required to revise their assignments inside the classroom based on the teacher’s WCF and were given 15 minutes while students in the control group only looked at the provided WCF without revising. It was ensured that both groups returned their papers to the instructor, and the instructor verified that the treatment group revised their drafts while the control group had not. Then, in week 6 (session 6), The immediate post-test was taken by all students in both groups. In week 14 (session 7), after an eight-week interval, all the students in both groups took the delayed post-test. Finally, in the last week, the teacher was interviewed three times (since it was a multi-session interview) after the experiment ended to answer research question four.

Table 3.1 *Study Procedures*

Session	Week	Group A	Group B
1	1	Students filled out a Background Questionnaire and did the Pilot study	Students filled out a Background Questionnaire and did the Pilot study
2	2	They wrote task 1 (Pretest)	They wrote task 1 (Pretest)
3	3	They revised task 1 and wrote	They had a look at task 1

		task 2	feedback for 5 minutes and wrote task 2
4	4	They revised task 2 and wrote task 3	They had a look at task 2 feedback for 5 minutes and wrote task 3
5	5	They revised task 3 and wrote task 4 (Immediate Posttest)	They had a look at task 3 feedback for 5 minutes and wrote task 4 (Immediate Posttest)
6	6,7,8, 9,10,11, 12,13	Interval	
7	14	They revised task 4 and wrote task 5 (Delayed posttest)	They had a look at task 4 feedback for 5 minutes and wrote task 5 (Delayed posttest)

3.3 Population and Sample

Study participants were university-level Kurdish students at one of the main public universities of College of Languages at English Department in Kurdistan (As a matter of ethical research, the university's name is not disclosed in order to protect the teacher from being traced). The sample was drawn from two second-year writing classes majoring in English Language and Literature. The age of the participants was between 19-23 years. The pre-test and background questionnaire were completed by sixty-two sophomore students (41 women and 21 men) in two different classes with the same number of 31 students in each group (i.e., control and treatment). With the exception of the revision requirement, all other factors were the same in both groups. The same instructor was teaching them. They both studied in the same college's English department as second-year learners, and they were given the same type and number of writing tasks. However, after the completion of the study, only 50 students were included, 25 from each of the two study

groups (36% male and 74 % female) because the rest were removed due to missing one or more episodes of data collection.

These participants were selected for a variety of reasons. To begin with, considering that there could be dropouts in the study, the sample size of the study was good because according to Dornyei (2007), each group should have at least 15 participants, while the groups each had 31 students. Additionally, they study writing as a separate subject in separate sessions while in other language centres and other EFL classes writing was merged with other language skills and taught in the same session; therefore, it would be difficult to test the accuracy of their writing in isolation. Furthermore, sophomore students were selected because their instructor rated their English language proficiency as intermediate. In order to understand and respond to the indirect WCF provided by the instructor, students need to have an intermediate level of language. To be enrolled in this program, these students had to meet specific requirements and then go through the process of interviews. Initially, students needed to achieve an average of at least 85 percent on their baccalaureate exam (12th-grade final exam required for tertiary education) and a minimum of 70 percent on their English subject test on the same test. After that, they must pass the standard internal test administered by the English department. Moreover, all the students, before enrolling in the university, they had studied English as an obligatory subject in the school for fourteen years.

3.4 Data Collection

For the purpose of collecting the data, three types of instruments were adopted: a background questionnaire, a quasi-experiment method (students were writing five writing tasks which acted as pre-test, two treatments, immediate post-test and delayed post-test) and a semi-structured interview which are explained in the following sections.

3.4.1 Background questionnaire

In the first week (session1), the students in both groups were given 15 minutes to answer a background questionnaire (see appendix 3) which was used to collect factual information about the respondents such as their demographic characteristics (age and gender), level of education, English language learning history and total time spent in learning English as L2.

3.4.2 Quasi-experiment

For fourteen weeks, the students wrote five essays of no less than 200 words in 45 minutes each. Some measures were put in place before the start of the experiment to avoid validity challenges and to assure reliable outcomes. Therefore, the researcher attempted to select two similar groups with a sufficient number of participants since according to Dornyei (2007) experimental studies should not have less than 15 participants.

The researcher, in the design of the quasi-experimental study, considered the criteria proposed by Campbell and Stanley (1963) to stay away from the threats to validity. The criteria are history, maturation, testing, instrumentation, regression to the mean, selection bias, the interplay of selection and maturation, the reactionary or interface impact of evaluation, as well as the reactionary impacts of experimental settings. First, in terms of history, no other event occurred other than the addition of the independent variable during the experiment; therefore, everything remained constant from beginning to the end. Second, maturation was controlled in the sense that, with the exception of the revision requirement, both the control and treatment groups went through the same identical procedure from start to finish. Furthermore, the process was not that lengthy to allow any type of maturation to occur. Third, the test was controlled in the sense that all the pre-test, immediate post-test and delayed post-test were from the same category, namely, argumentative essays with the same word limit (minimum of 200 words) but different topics (Friendship for the pretest, Fashion for the immediate post-test and Fear for the delayed post-test). Fourth, the instrumentation was genuine since the measuring techniques were not altered in the sense that both groups received the same tests, which were observed and scored by the same teacher. Fifth, the regression to the mean was achieved by randomly assigning two groups not based on extreme scores. Furthermore, the participants were not selected in a biased manner since the two groups had already been split in the first semester, and the study was conducted in the second semester, thereby the treatment and control groups were assigned at random. Seventh, when it comes to the mortality rate, though some participants dropped out, the researcher had already left a decent margin of safety by selecting 64 participants, which was later reduced to 49. Eighth, as a result of the availability of two already separated classes, the selection-maturation interaction threat has been neutralized. Ninth, the "reactive or interaction effect of testing" was unaffected in this study since the treatment began after the pre-test, rather than before. Finally, the experimental setups had no

influence on the research since the students' assignments and replies were already part of their classes; they were not added for the purpose of the study (they were only required to revise the tasks which were already planned to be administered).

In the light of the above considerations, the quasi-experiment procedure was as follows: After collecting background information of the participants in the first week (session 1), in week 2 (session 2) the quasi-experiment started when both groups were required to write task 1 which acted as the pre-test which was an argumentative essay. It was decided to select argumentative essays since this essay genre requires more creativity to persuade the reader, which requires more language input on the students' part (Zhu,2001). Then the teacher collected their writing and took it home for providing WCF on the students' writing about grammatical accuracy using a scoring rubric (see section 3.5 below for the scoring rubric). The teacher provided indirect selective coded feedback on three grammatical error types which are English article system (AS), subject-verb agreement (SVA) and verb form (VF). After providing the WCF (see appendix 4 for a sample), in week 3 (session 3) the teacher returned the papers to the students in both groups. The treatment group was required to revise and rewrite their whole writing based on the provided feedback in 15 minutes (see appendix 5 for a sample) while the control group was only required to have a look at the teacher's feedback to see their errors but without revising it. Then in the same session, the students in both groups were asked to write a second essay (task 2) in 45 minutes.

After the teacher collected the papers and provided feedback in the manner explained earlier, the papers were brought back to the students in week 4 (session 4). Again, the treatment group was required to revise and rewrite their essay while the control was not. Then, during the same session, the students of both groups were requested to write task 3 and submit it to the teacher for his feedback at home.

After that in week 5 (session 5), the students in the treatment group revised their task 3, and students in the control group only looked at the provided feedback, then they were required to write down task 4 (which acted as the immediate post-test). In week 6 (session 6), the task was returned to both groups where the treatment group revised their writings, but the control group did not. However, in this session, none of the groups were required to write the last task which acted as the post-test because the researcher had decided to

give an eight-week interval between task 4 and task 5 (the post-test) in order to check if revision can have long term effects and can be transferred to new pieces of writing after an interval. Finally, in week 14 (session 7), both groups were required to write another argumentative essay in 45 minutes. After finishing writing, the papers were handed to the teacher to be marked using the scoring rubric mentioned earlier to use the results as the post-test to be compared with the results of the pre-test.

3.4.3 Semi-Structured Interview

Semi-structured interview was conducted to collect in-depth data about the reflection of the teacher on the revised version of the students (see Appendix 7). The semi-structured interview is the most used interview type in applied linguistics research as it offers a balance between the other two extremes (structured vs. unstructured interviews) (Kallio, Pietila, Johnson & Kangasniemi, 2016). Although there are some guiding questions and probes by the interviewer in the semi-structured interview, they are open-ended and allow the interviewee to elaborate upon them (Kallio et al., 2016). The semi-structured interview was designed in multiple session forms including three different meetings. Polkinghorne (2005, as cited in Dornyei, 2007, p.135) asserts that a single-shot interview does not provide full and rich descriptions; thus, in order to “obtain sufficient depth and breadth”, multiple session interviews were preferred. The interview questions were designed with regard to considering all the aspects related to the insights of the teacher towards the revision practice and its effects. Before conducting the interview with the teacher, the content validity of the interview questions was checked by the supervisor then the questions were piloted with the teacher to determine if any modifications are needed. As a result, the questions were restructured because they were leading questions or were not directly related to answering the research question. Also, after each session, extra questions were added thinking about the teacher's answer as probe questions for the next session.

Moreover, the research ethics were also considered, and the participant was informed of his right to be kept anonymous and confidential, and that he could withdraw from the study at any time. As such, his name was not disclosed, and the consent form was filled out (see appendix 4). The interviews were administered during and after the experimental study was finished in three sessions. The first session was conducted after two treatment sessions then the second interview session was carried out after the fourth

treatment session and finally, the last interview session was conducted at the end of the experimental study. The aim was to enable the teacher to experience the whole process to have a deep understanding and reflection on the revised version of the students' writings. The interviews were administered at the university in the English language as the teacher was a proficient speaker of English. The interviews were recorded after obtaining the teacher's permission and then transcribed. Each of the three sessions of the interview lasted around fifteen to twenty minutes. The first session was to break the ice between the researcher and the teacher and acted as a pilot interview where the interview questions were restructured, and the teacher understood what the interview is about. In the second session, a more polished version of the questions was asked, and more accurate and comprehensive answers were presented. Between the second and the third session and after transcribing the interview, the researcher considered all the answers and then prepared some follow-up questions to gain answers for some minute details. Finally, the third session was conducted, and the follow-up questions were asked.

3.5 Scoring Rubric

Scoring essays and marking them is a subjective process; therefore, some steps needed to be taken into consideration in order to reach a standard level of scoring and reliable results for both groups' writings. In the first step, the same instructor, who was teaching the class and had more than twenty-five years of teaching experience, was assigned to score the papers. The reason for choosing the teacher was that he was aware of the program, its objectives, and the materials for teaching as he had been teaching writing classes for more than twenty years. The second step was to prepare a rubric for scoring the papers to throw doubts about the reliability of scoring and to follow an analytic rating method. The rubric also sought to demonstrate consistent progress in students' grammatical accuracy between the pretest and posttest by determining each student's grade shift between them.

The scoring rubric was adopted from Shintani and Ellis (2013) and Shintani et al (2014). In the scoring rubric, first, the number of obligatory occasions (i.e., when the use of the target-like feature is unavoidable) is counted. Then, the number of correct forms of the grammatical categories was counted. Finally, the number of the correct forms was divided by the number of obligatory occasions and multiplied by 100 to achieve the score of accuracy for each grammatical category as follows:

Figure 1

n correct forms of the grammatical category (ex. SVA)

x 100

n obligatory occasions (ex. For using SVA)

This procedure was used as the scoring rubric to grade each grammatical category (AS, SVA, VF) separately, and then the three scores were added together to determine the final score for each task.

The third step was to explain and discuss with the teacher the scoring and rating process, although he was well acquainted with it, so as to ensure to arrive at the required scales. Finally, for the purpose of intra-rater reliability, the writing of ten participants from both groups from both pretest and posttest (total of 40 papers) were copied before the teacher rates them. Then, after two months they were given back to the same teacher to remark and eliminate any bias and achieve intra-rater reliability (Kang & Rubin 2012).

3.6 Data Analysis

It was pertinent for this study to apply different methods of analysis based on various kinds of data collection. The following subsections describe how the quantitative and qualitative data were analysed.

3.6.1 Analysis of Quantitative Data

The subject instructor scored the pre-test, immediate post-test, and delayed post-test for both the treatment and control group (the instructor scored 75 essays for each group, 25 for each test) using the adapted scoring rubric stated in section (3.5) above as a first step. Before inputting the scores into IBM SPSS 26, the rater assessed each grammatical category (AS, SVA, VF) separately for each essay, then summed the three scores to obtain an average grammatical accuracy score. Four main tests were needed to be run in the SPSS which are detailed in the following paragraph. Before running each of the above tests, One-Sample Kolmogorov-Smirnov tests were run for each of the above-mentioned groups separately to check the normality of data distribution ($p > 0.05$ two-tailed). Dornyei (2007) states that “normal distribution means that some of the values are low, some high, and the

bulk of the values are centred around the middle” to form a “bell-shaped curve” (p.208). Normality test is regarded as a crucial step in the process of data analysis as it assists in decisions about the “statistical methods for data analysis” and drawing “meaningful conclusions” (Mishra et al., 2019, p. 67).

After running the normality test and finding out if the data is normally distributed, an independent sample t-test ($p < 0.05$ two-tailed) was run for the pretest only for both treatment and control groups to make sure that the writing level of these two groups was not statistically significant to each other before the start of the treatment. After that, the second independent sample t-test was run to check if the treatment group has generally outperformed the control group between the pretest and immediate posttest (to find out if revision has been effective). Then the third test was run which was a 2-independent sample t-test (the non-parametric test of Mann-Whitney U) between pre-test and delayed posttest to check if there has been a long-term effect of the treatment (to find out if revision had a long-term effect). Finally, the fourth test, which was Repeated Measures ANOVA was run to compare gain scores (posttest score – Pretest score) of the three groups (AS, SVA and VF) in terms of improvement due to receiving the treatment (to see which grammatical accuracy category has been majorly affected by the revision).

3.6.2 Analysis of Qualitative Data

The researcher transcribed the interview recordings into text and then compared the transcription to the recordings to determine their accuracy. Consequently, 6545 words were typed into the computer from the interviews. The transcripts from the interviews were then analysed using a thematic analysis approach. Braun and Clarke (2006) define thematic analysis as the process of identifying, analysing, and reporting relevant data (themes) where the collected data will be organized and defined in detail at a professional level. They further state that although thematic analysis is “a poorly demarcated and rarely acknowledged, yet widely used qualitative analytic method” (2006, p. 4). In order to analyse the interview data, the researcher followed the outline set forth by Braun and Clarke (2006) which consists of six phases, which are detailed below:

Being well informed about the data: The researcher listened to the entire audio twice attentively, then read the transcription carefully. After that, the researchers started reading

for the second time, while reading, the researcher highlighted interesting parts and wrote down ideas.

Generating initial codes: the researcher worked on the highlighted parts and the noted ideas and coded them. Then, he collected relevant data (extracts) for each code.

Searching for themes: after having a long list of codes, the researcher considered the relationship between codes and then categorized them into themes. In this phase, visual representation (tables) of the codes was used to assist in the classification. Initially, some codes were combined to form main themes or subthemes while some others were discarded because they did not belong to the themes as such, they were classified under a category named miscellaneous. Accordingly, the extracts were classified based on that categorization.

Reviewing the themes: in this phase, the themes were re-evaluated to check if they are in concord with the codes and the collated extracts. Once extracts and the codes were compared against the themes, some extracts appeared to not fit into the themes as such either the theme was reworked by rewriting it or creating sub-themes or new themes were created to encompass those extracts and data. Then, the new classification of the themes after this refinement was re-read to make sure that they are relevant to all the data and that they have enough support data.

Defining and naming themes: the researcher analysed and described each theme separately in order to identify which part of the data was analysed by it. Following this, the titles of the themes were changed to reflect their respective themes.

Before stepping towards phase 6, another extra step was regarded for the sake of the validity of themes which was handing the themes, codes and the supporting extracts to the supervisor. The supervisor re-examined all the list where some themes were divided into further sub-themes while some others were disregarded.

Producing the report: After having the final version of the themes and data set (extracts) that represent them, the researcher started to provide the final description and analysis of each theme by providing vivid extracts to it and relating it to the research questions.

Table 3.6 *Illustrations of Creating Three Separate Themes*

Participant's answer	Codes	Initial themes	Established themes
Teacher: "There's no doubt. Uh, that it (revision) is effective, successful. And useful because you know, the students would be involved in more activities. It is not just to review their mistakes and come to write a new one. So, when. Would review the previous assignments in order to see their mistakes and then come to revise the old composition Then this is a good opportunity The teacher gives to students, to, you know, to put into practice or to correct their mistakes."	The teacher believes that revision encourages students to engage in more practice and apply what they have learned.	The perception of the teacher was positive towards revision requirement, and it was effective on improving L2 students' writing grammatical accuracy	Demanding Students to Revise Is Effective and Useful.
Teacher: "because of the type of feedback, I attribute this problem to this point that my students might not have understood fully what they meant. There are individual differences between the students, some students don't care about what you teach about what you explained."	Students had individual differences in their background knowledge.	Some students were unable to implement teachers' comments	Students face difficulties in implementing teachers' comments
Teacher: "And another reason is pertinent to lack of information. Okay. So, um, how this issue can be solved in the future, in my opinion, the teacher might give more explanation about these grammatical mistakes and the codes that he uses in marking to the students to give more explanation about these things."	The teachers need to provide more explanations to the students about the grammatical structures and the codes.	There were some suggestions made by the teacher regarding how to improve the effectiveness of revision practice	The teacher's suggestions to improve the revision practice.

Chapter 4: Findings and Discussion

This study employed both qualitative and quantitative methods to collect data for answering the four research questions of the study. Since the quantitative method gives extensive technical apparatus and the qualitative method delivers deeper and richer data, “a mixed approach can offer additional benefits for the understanding the phenomenon in question” (Dornyei, 2007, p. 47). The results will be more thorough and understandable because the qualitative data will explain the "how" and "why" of the quantitative results. The qualitative section provides the instructor the opportunity to discuss his thoughts, beliefs, perceptions, and experiences related to the same variable, while the quantitative part delivers objective and numerical results. This chapter consists of three sections in order to present the collected data and discuss them. In the first two sections (4.1 & 4.2) both the results of the quasi-experiment and the emerging themes of the teacher interview are presented. Then, in the following section (4.3) the results are discussed.

4.1 Findings of the Quasi-Experiment

In order to answer the first three research questions of the study, the pre-test (first written task), immediate post-test (fourth written task to compare with the results of the first task), and delayed post-test (fifth written task after eight-weeks-interval to compare with the results of first written task) results of 25 students from each of the study groups were analysed. Mainly, after running the normality test for each and determining the type of inferential test required, four SPSS tests were needed to analyse the data, which are summarized below:

First test: through running an independent sample t-test the results of the pre-test of both the treatment group and control group were compared to ensure that the groups writing levels were not statistically significant from each other before the start of the treatment (see 4.1.1).

Second test: for answering the first research question, which sought “What is the effect of Indirect Corrective Feedback (ICF) with revision on the grammatical accuracy of L2 students’ writing?”, the results of both the treatment group and control group in the pre-test and immediate post-test were compared by running independent sample t-tests (see 4.1.2).

Third test: in order to answer the second research question, which is “What is the long-term effect of ICF with revision on the improvement of L2 students’ grammatical accuracy?”, the results of both the treatment group and control group in the pre-test and delayed post-test were compared by running independent sample t-tests (see 4.1.3).

Fourth test: Repeated Measures -Mixed ANOVA test was run to compare the mean scores results achieved in the pre-test and delayed post-test for each grammatical category (AS, SVA, VF) by the treatment group to answer the third research question, which is “How does revision affect different types of grammatical features of L2 students’ writing?” (See 4.1.4).

4.1.1 Effect of Revision on Grammatical Accuracy of L2 Students’ Writing

To check if the writing levels of the treatment and control group were not significantly different from each other before the start of the treatment, their results in the pre-test were compared. The first step was to run the normality test using Kolmogorov-Smirnov Test to decide on the inferential statistics to be run (See table 4.1 below).

Table 4.1 *Kolmogorov-Smirnov Test for Treatment Group and Control Group Scores*

Group	Kolmogorov-Smirnova			Shapiro-Wilk		
	Statistic	Df	Sig.	Statistic	df	Sig.
Pretest Treatment Group	.153	25	.135	.886	25	.009
Control Group	.163	25	.086	.885	25	.009

As shown in Table 4.1, the data for the pre-test of the treatment and control group is normally distributed because the p values of both treatment and control groups are greater than 0.05 ($p = .135$ and $p = .086$, respectively). Having normally distributed data led the researcher to run a parametric test (Independent-Samples T-Test) to find out whether the treatment group and control group writing levels were significantly different or not before the intervention of revision plus WCF (see table 4.2 & 4.3).

Table 4.2 Comparing Pre-test Mean Scores for the Study Groups through Independent-Samples T Test

Group	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean
Treatment Group	25	84.12	9.989	1.998
Control Group	25	87.08	8.893	1.779

As shown in Table 4.2, the mean score of both the treatment group and control group was $M = 84.12$, $M = 87.08$, respectively. It can be noticed that the mean scores are close to each other because the difference between both groups is only 2.96 marks out of a possible 100 marks; however, to examine if the difference is statistically different, an Independent - sample T-test is run (See Table 4.3).

Table 4.3 Independent-Sample T-test to Compare the Means of the Pre-test of Both Groups.

t-test for Equality of Means							
	T	df	Sig.2 tailed)	Mean Difference	Std.Error Difference	95% Confidence Interval of the Differenc Lower Upper	
Equal variances assumed	-1.107	48	.274	-2.960	2.675	-8.338	2.418
Equal variances not assumed	-1.107	47.36	.274	-2.960	2.675	-8.340	2.420

The results in Table 4.3 illustrate that the pre-test of both the treatment group and control group were not significantly different from each other ($t=-1.107$), $p = 0.274$ two-tailed, $p > 0.05$), which means that both groups were equivalent in terms of writing accuracy level before the start of the intervention. Considering that the writing skills of the treatment group and control group were not significantly different before the effect of the intervention, hence, the results of the posttest of both control and treatment groups could be compared to answer the research questions one, two and three (see below 4.1.2, 4.1.3 & 4.1.4).

A comparison of the results of the pre-test and immediate post-test of both the treatment and control groups was conducted to determine whether revision had improved

the grammatical accuracy of the treatment group. Initially, the normality test was run for the immediate post-test (as for the pre-test results, the normality test was run in the previous section) using Kolmogorov-Smirnov to determine which inferential statistics should be run (See table 4.4 below).

Table 4.4 *Kolmogorov-Smirnov Test for Treatment Group and Control Group scores in the immediate posttest.*

Group		Kolmogorov-Smirnova			Shapiro-Wilk		
		Statistic	Df	Sig.	Statistic	df	Sig.
Immediate Posttest	Treatment Group	.215	25	.004	.867	25	.004
	Control Group	.259	25	.000	.623	25	.000

The data for the immediate post-test of the treatment and control group is not normally distributed because p values are smaller than 0.05 ($p = .004$ and $p = .000$ respectively). Not having normally distributed data led the researcher to run a non-parametric test (T Test-Mann-Whitney U) to find out whether the revision had any effect on the scores of the treatment group in the immediate post-test (see table 4.5 & 4.6).

Table 4.5 *Comparisons of the Means Scores of the Pre-test and Immediate Post-test of Both Groups Through Two Independent-Samples T Test.*

Group		N	Mean Rank	Sum of Ranks
Pretest	Treatment Group	25	23.08	577.00
	Control Group	25	24.92	698.00
	Total	50		
Immediate Posttest	Treatment Group	25	32.12	803.00
	Control Group	25	25.88	472.00
	Total	50		

As illustrated above in table 4.5, the results show that the mean rank of the treatment group between the pre-test and immediate post-test has increased from $m=23.08$ to $m=32.12$ while the mean rank of the control group has climbed slightly from $m= 24.92$ to $m=25.88$. In other words, the treatment group improved 9.04 marks out of 100 possible points, whereas the control group improved only 0.96 points. These results are compared to each other through the following Mann-Whitney U test to see if their differences are statistically significant.

Table 4.6 *Mann-Whitney U Test to Compare the Pre-test and Delayed Post-test of Both Groups.*

	Pretest	Immediate Posttest
Mann-Whitney U	158.000	252.000
Wilcoxon W	441.000	577.000
Z	-1.176	-3.225
Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed)	.240	.001

As shown in Table 4.6, the results of the treatment group and control group were significantly different from each other in the immediate post-test because $p < 0.05$ ($p = 0.001$ two-tailed). In other words, the treatment group scored higher than the control group. This means that the grammatical accuracy improvement of the treatment group was significantly higher than the improvement of the control group. This significant difference between the treatment group and control group in both pre-test and immediate post-test proves that the intervention (i.e., revision after WCF) is effective in enhancing the grammatical accuracy of L2 students' writing. This finding answers the first research question. In order to answer the second research question, the following subsection is allocated.

4.1.2 Long-term Impact of Revision on L2 Students' Grammatical Accuracy

To assess whether revision had a long-term effect on the grammatical accuracy of the treatment group, the results of the pre-test and delayed post-test of both the treatment and control groups were compared after the eight-week interval. A normality test was run for the

delayed post-test (as for the pre-test results, the normality test was run in section 4.1.1) using the Kolmogorov-Smirnov test in order to determine which inferential statistics should be run (See table 4.7 below):

Table 4.7 *Kolmogorov-Smirnov Test for Treatment Group and Control Group Scores in the Delayed Posttest*

Group		Kolmogorov-Smirnova			Shapiro-Wilk		
		Statistic	Df	Sig.	Statistic	df	Sig.
Delayed Posttest	Treatment Group	.112	25	.200	.931	25	.094
	Control Group	.163	25	.086	.885	25	.009

Table 4.7 shows that the data for the delayed post-test of the treatment and control group is normally distributed because the p-value is greater than 0.05 ($p = .200$ and $p = .086$ respectively). Having normally distributed data led the researcher to run a parametric test (Independent-Samples T-Test) to find out whether revision had a long-term effect on the scores of the treatment group in the delayed post-test after the two-months interval (see table 4.8 & 4.9).

Table 4.8 *Means Scores of the Pre-test and Delayed Posttest of Both Groups*

	Group	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Mean
Pretest	Treatment Group	25	84.12	9.989	1.998
	Control Group	25	87.08	8.893	1.779
Delayed Posttest	Treatment Group	25	91.36	7.117	1.423
	Control Group	25	84.68	10.546	2.109

The above table indicates that the mean score of both the treatment group and control group in the delayed post-test was $M = 91.36$ and $M = 84.68$, respectively which means that the treatment group scored higher than the control group. In other words, after an eight-week interval, the treatment group still scored 6.68 points higher than the control

group on a scale of 100 possible points. Therefore, to check if this difference was statistically significant, the following independent sample T-test was run.

Table 4.9 *Independent-Sample T-test to Compare the Pre-test and Delayed Post-test of Both Groups*

		t-test for Equality of Means					95% Confidence	
		t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Difference	Std. Error Difference	Interval of the Difference	
						Lower	Upper	
Pretest	Equal variances assumed	-1.107	48	.274	-2.960	2.675	-8.338	2.418
	Equal variances not assumed	-1.107	47.3	.274	-2.960	2.675	-8.340	2.420
Delayed Posttest	Equal variances assumed	2.625	48	.012	6.680	2.545	1.564	11.796
	Equal variances not assumed	2.625	42.1	.012	6.680	2.545	1.545	11.815

The above table indicates that the results of the pretest and delayed posttest were significantly different, ($t(48) = 2.265$, $p = 0.012$ two-tailed, $p < 0.05$). This means that the grammatical accuracy improvement of the treatment group was significantly higher than the improvement of the control group in the delayed post-test. This significant difference between the treatment group and control group in both pre-test and delayed post-test proves that the intervention (i.e., revision after WCF) has a long-term effect on improving grammatical accuracy in writing tasks. In other words, after revising their essays in four treatment sessions and taking another test after two months-interval, learners in the treatment group scored higher than the control group ($M=91.36$; $M=84.68$, respectively), indicating that their essays were more grammatically accurate. This means that still, the

grammatical accuracy of the treatment group students kept being improved as compared to their scores in the pre-test. In response to the second research question, this finding indicates that revising texts by students improves their grammatical accuracy in the long run. As we learn that revision does produce benefits in new writing and this can last over time, the question arises as to whether this effect of the revision can be the same for different Grammatical Features (GF). This is the third research question of the study, which is addressed in the below subsection.

4.1.3 The Impact of Revision on Different GF of L2 Students' Writing

In order to check whether there is any difference in the effect of revision on different Grammatical Features (GF) of L2 students' writing, the mean score results of the treatment group for each grammatical category (AS, SVA, VF) in the pre-test and delayed posttest were compared. The first step was to have the gain scores for each of the above-mentioned grammatical categories (GC) to be able to run the Repeated Measures Mixed ANOVA test.

The gain scores were calculated by using Compute Variable function in SPSS. To compute the difference scores, it was needed to subtract the pretest score for each individual GC from the post-test score. Once the gain scores for each GC were achieved, the Repeated Measures Mixed ANOVA test was run (see Table 4.10 & 4.11).

Table 4.10 *Gain Score Results of the Treatment Group for Each Grammatical Category in the Pre-test and Delayed Post-test*

	Mean	Std. Deviation	N
AS_gain	15.2320	22.05801	50
SVA_gain	4.8800	9.01914	50
VF_gain	1.4800	8.70899	50

Table 4.10 above indicates that the gain scores from the pre-test and delayed post-test were $M = 15.23$, $M = 4.88$, and $M = 1.48$ for each of the grammatical categories (AS, SVA, VF), respectively. In other words, as compared to their pretest scores, the treatment group scored 15.23 points higher in AS, 4.88 points higher in SVA, and only 1.48 points

higher in VF out of a possible 100 points. This means that there have been different means scores for each of the grammatical accuracies which is further tested and interpreted in the below table.

Table 4.11. *Test of Within-subjects Effects of the Treatment Group for Each Grammatical Category*

Source	Type III Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Partial Eta Squared	
Gain	Sphericity Assumed	8786.541	2	4393.270	20.316	.000	.293
	Greenhouse-Geisser	8786.541	1.477	5949.363	20.316	.000	.293
	Huynh-Feldt	8786.541	1.512	5812.059	20.316	.000	.293
	Lower-bound	8786.541	1.000	8786.541	20.316	.000	.293
Error (Gain)	Sphericity Assumed	21192.033	98	216.245			
	Greenhouse-Geisser	21192.033	72.367	292.839			
	Huynh-Feldt	21192.033	74.077	286.081			
	Lower-bound	21192.033	49.000	432.490			

The results in Table 4.11 indicate that the difference between the gain scores of different grammatical features is statistically significant ($F(2,98) = 20.31, p = 0.000$ two-tailed, $p < 0.05$). This means that the impact of the revision on different grammatical features is different from one category to the other. To determine which feature was more affected, the comparison of their gain scores shown in Table 4.10 indicates that the gain scores from the pre-test and delayed post-test were $M = 15.23$, $M = 4.88$, and $M = 1.48$ for each of the grammatical categories (AS, SVA, VF), respectively. This means that the most impact of

revision was on AS ($m= 15.23$) and then on SVA ($m=4.88$) while the least effect of revision was on VF ($m=1.48$). This significant difference between mean scores achieved in the pre-test and delayed post-test for each grammatical category (AS, SVA, VF) by the treatment group proves that the intervention (i.e., revision after WCF) can be more effective in improving the grammatical accuracy of AS compared to the other ones. This finding answers the third research question.

By and large, the quantitative results revealed that asking students to revise their writing improves their L2 writing grammatical accuracy and that this effect can sustain in the long run in new writing pieces. Moreover, it proved that the impact level of revision varies from one grammatical feature to another. After answering the three research questions related to the quantitative part of the study by running SPSS tests, now it is due time to answer the fourth and last research question in the following section (4.2) via the obtained data from the semi-structured interview.

4.2 Findings of the Semi-Structured Interview

This section presents the results of the data collected from a multi-session interview with the subject teacher. Therefore, thematic analysis was used to analyse the transcriptions from the interviews. Findings are reported in this section to answer the fourth research question of this thesis, which is “What is the perception of teachers towards the process and effect of revision on students’ writing?”. As a result of a scrutinized validation process conducted by the supervisor and researcher, the generated themes were carefully examined and confirmed. According to this methodology, the qualitative data were categorized into themes, and where necessary, in sub-themes. The researcher emphasizes certain parts of the quotation by using bold typeface, but the quotations are presented without correction.

4.2.1 Theme one: Demanding Students to Revise is Effective and Useful

The interviewed teacher believes that asking students to revise their writings can accelerate the effectiveness of the provided written CF and make it obtain its utmost benefits. The effectiveness of revision after WCF was revealed in the quasi-experimental study as well. The mean score of the immediate post-test ($M=32.12$) of the treatment group was higher

than the mean score of the control group (M=25.88) (see table 4.5). In the same vein, the teacher's positive beliefs which emerged in the interview sessions originated from certain reasoning are discussed in the following four subthemes.

4.2.1.1 Students Have a Positive Reflection on Revision

The interviewed teacher reported that students had a positive reaction towards practicing revision of their writings based on the teacher's provided WCF. Although students faced difficulties during this practice since this is a new practice, this novelty encouraged them to continue trying it. When the interviewed teacher was asked about the students' reflection on the revision practice, he reported the following:

+ "as a matter of fact, and in the light of what my students did in their writing and their reaction. The reaction of my students to submit the revised vision of their written assignment was in general positive. But, you know, um, my students you know, needed explanation of the Codes that I use in marking and in giving my feedback about their mistakes, uh, but, uh, in general, their reaction was positive" (Teacher).

The teacher furthered highlighting the positive attitude of the students despite having difficulty with the new system, saying that:

+ "It was something new. So, at first, it was difficult for them, they were asking a lot of questions, but as I explained to them what they should do, explained the meaning of the codes of the feedback, then they accepted the idea, and they were very happy. They were very pleased to go on" (Teacher).

This statement by the instructor indicates that since requiring students to revise their writings is a new practice for them, the teacher had to explain the aims, the procedures, and the requirement of the whole process to the students. The more students understand what is expected of them and how to accomplish it, the more likely they will be to comply.

This positive view of students is due to the fact that it leads to engaging the students in the process of writing better as such their motivation is increased, and they feel they are part of the whole process, and they are not mere receivers. The interviewed teacher mentioned some of these reasons that have made the revision practice effective which are described in the following subthemes.

4.2.1.2 Higher Level of Engagement

There are occasions where the teacher's provided WCF is not applied and goes unnoticed. This is mainly due to the fact that students are not required to submit a revised version of the writing based on the teacher's WCF. In the interview, when the teacher was asked about his perception of the revision requirement, he stated the following:

+ "There's no doubt. Uh, that it (revision) is effective, successful. And useful because you know, the students would be involved in more activities" (Teacher)

As it is stated by the interviewed teacher, asking students to submit a new revised version of their previous writing involves the students in more practice which increases the chances of deeper engagement in the process of learning the grammatical structures.

Moreover, once the students are required to revise, they will be engaged in the activity of improving the writing based on the WCF provided by the teacher. Revising also provides a practical opportunity for the students to apply their newly learned writing structures.

The teacher believed that the benefit of better student engagement in this activity leads to noticing the errors and their correct forms. This was clearly stated by the teacher once he was requested to explain why he thinks revision is effective as shown below:

+ "It is not just to review their mistakes and come to write a new one. So, when students review the previous assignments in order to see their mistakes and then come to revise the old composition Then this is a good opportunity The teacher gives to students to notice their mistakes and see where the gap was and where the mistakes were made" (Teacher).

This statement by the teacher implies that it would be easier for students to engage in correcting their mistakes when they consciously understand the nature of their mistakes, which is the first step towards correcting them. In addition to the students' higher engagement, the next reason for the revision practice's effectiveness is students' motivation which is explained in the next subtheme.

4.2.1.3 Increasing Students' Motivation

The results from the interview with the teacher revealed that the students get more motivated due to the feedback and revision requirement. By revising their work, students can improve the quality of the pieces they have already written. This can be noticed in the following comment by the teacher saying:

+ “concerning the revision that my students provided I can say that. I think that a part that revision to the process of writing a composition was a good step in the right direction, It was a very good thing. It was a new experience. Um, in such a way that both the teacher and the students, highly benefited from it, the students had a good opportunity to be motivated to review the mistakes that the teacher had indicated a good opportunity to revise the writing in order to correct their mistakes” (Teacher).

. This is because they will have the opportunity to turn the theoretical linguistic knowledge, they have acquired through the WCF, into actual writing. Once students are part of the whole process, where they take care of their writing and improving its quality, they will be motivated to practice more writing. Engaging students in the subject and involving them in the actual writing process and its improvement increases their motivation to learn. As their motivation increases, the process becomes more student-centred, and their willingness to follow up on the WCF grows. The increase of L2 writing learners' motivation is the driving force that pushes the students forward to achieve their goals and acquire the structures. Without motivation, it will be difficult for even individuals with a high aptitude to achieve their learning goals. In the same regard the teacher also added that:

+ “when it comes, um, to the reaction of the students about, um, about revising and resubmitting their compositions, you know, they were eager to start the task, especially this was obvious in the second and the following tasks. They were asking for their results, they liked to know what they have done, and they, I mean, they loved to practice more and see how they have improved” (Teacher).

The above quotation from the subject teacher explains how students were motivated by investing time and effort in this practice. It also explains how it guided them toward their goals by initiating revision activities and persisting with them. This increase of motivation was not only for the students, but it was evident in the teacher as well which is addressed in the following subsection.

4.2.1.4 Increasing Teacher's Motivation

The results of the teacher interview revealed that revision practice following WCF motivates the teachers to carry on providing more WCF to their students. Asking students to revise assures the teacher that the provided WCF will not go unnoticed or neglected because once students are required to revise, they are obliged to pay attention to the teachers' provided WCF and apply it in the corrected version as it was reported by the teacher in the following quote:

+ "As far as the teacher is (the teacher talks about himself in the third person) concerned, the teacher also benefited from this new development by ensuring that his marking his feedback had been useful by considering the progress that the students would make in, uh, in their writing" (Teacher)

The above quote demonstrates that by submitting a new revised version of the students' writings, the teacher can determine the extent to which the WCF has influenced the students' writing accuracy, which in turn inspires the instructor to continue providing WCF to their students.

When the teacher was asked to explain what he liked particularly about demanding revision based on his WCF, he reported the following:

+ "well, I have to say that previously, certain things were demotivating me, us, from providing more feedback. These things were times when my students did not consider my correction and they were, you know, repeating the same errors due to not paying attention to my feedback. Also, um, by providing or asking them to revise I knew for certain that my feedback had been looked at by the student because he or she was obliged to submit a revised version. As a matter of fact, when I saw their writing is improving, I was even happier than before to provide my students with more feedback" (Teacher).

This statement by the teacher explains that once the teacher has the chance of looking at the revised version of the students' writing, he can observe to what extent his WCF and his techniques for teaching writing have been successful and his hard work has not been pointless due to students' ignorance of the comments. To sum up, the reason which led the teacher to believe that the revision process is effective in improving learners'

grammatical accuracy is its contribution to; escalating students' engagement in the process of learning; rising students' motivation; and better motivating the teacher as well.

4.2.2 Theme Two: Students Face Difficulties in Implementing Teachers' Comments

Implementing the revision practice is not an easy task for both teachers and students since there are challenges and difficulties facing the process. These difficulties which are explained and categorized in the following subthemes, if not dealt with, will decrease the impact of the whole process of revision and WCF and make it less beneficial.

4.2.2.1 Students' Limited Grammatical Knowledge Complicates Understanding of the Codes

When students are required to revise based on the provided WCF, the most vital factor which affects the success of the practice is the comprehension of the WCF and the correction. In the Indirect WCF, the errors are coded, and it is the students' duty to understand the code and correct the erroneous structure based on that code. This requires the students to have accumulated readily available grammatical background knowledge to understand the code and then to be able to self-correct themselves on that base. However, as it is reported below by the interviewed teacher, a few students, due to their limited grammatical knowledge, were unable to understand the revision requirement:

+ "because of the type of the feedback, I attribute this problem to this point that my students might not have understood fully what they meant. There are individual differences between the students, some students don't care about what you teach about what you explained. Though I explained in the beginning the nature of feedback and the codes that I would use in marking and giving my feedback. But, you know, until the fourth assignment, my students, from time to time, would ask me about the meaning of the codes that I use in my feedback. So, this was one of the difficulties. Yeah, my students face difficulty in understanding the codes of feedback" (Teacher).

The above quote revealed that the low level of students' grammatical background knowledge makes it difficult to understand the coded WCF which in return the students will fail to revise their piece of writing. Moreover, as it is stated by the subject teacher, the students' low level of grammatical knowledge creates problems for the teacher while

attempting to implement his/her WCF and require students to rewrite. Even though the teacher repeatedly had explained the codes to the students but still some students failed to understand them and nevertheless, ask for more explanation. This issue was detected in the quasi-experimental study as well which was shown in table 4.10. The results indicated that students gained the least improvement in the VF grammatical error category ($m=1.48$) as compared to AS grammatical error category ($m=15.23$). This was because the students did not have enough knowledge about the structure of the VF as such, they were rewriting the error as it is. Moreover, when the teacher was asked about the students' reaction once they failed to understand the codes or to know the correct form, he stated the following:

+ “ok, before replying to this question, I want to make one point clear, which is, uh, this problem was by a few students while the majority of students were, you know, doing well. Coming back to your question, you see, the students, hm, who did not understand the codes, they were asking a lot of repetitive questions about the same things. Some were skipping or not submitting the revised version. Some, you know, some students were submitting it without changing the errors” (Teacher).

This statement from the teacher explained the fact that this issue was experienced by a small number of students while the rest were coping with the revision requirements. The consequences of not understanding the correct structure and the codes by the students included asking the same questions over and over, leaving out the revision task, or even rewriting without correction (as discussed in the next subtheme).

4.2.2.2 Rewriting the Text With no Improvement Due to Low Grammatical Knowledge and Lack of Interest

There are occasions when students understand the code and the requirements of the teacher but still, they cannot attend the correct form due to their low level of background information about the grammatical structures. When they fail to know the correct structure, they cannot self-correct themselves as such cannot revise the composition and they submit the same thing without improving and correcting it. This means that the whole attempt is of no benefit to the students since no improvement is achieved. The teacher reports this issue in the following quotation:

+ “at the beginning of each task, I reminded my students of the codes that I use in, in, in

giving my feedback, but still some students, they were not, there are still some students who don't understand, especially when they revise, they rewrite their writing, but without correcting their mistakes. I showed them their mistakes through the codes, but when they revised, they were writing the same thing. They rewrite the same thing without correcting them" (Teacher).

Although it was stated earlier that students are motivated to take part in implementing the practice of revision after receiving WCF. However, there are some students who are not interested in following the WCF and rewriting their tasks due to their low grammatical knowledge. This leads the learner to neglect the task and the whole process of revision and correction as it is reported by the teacher below:

+ "As you know in the previous interview, I explained that some of my students until the fourth assignment had difficulty in understanding the codes and difficulty in how to correct their mistakes. Well, if you ask me about the reason then, uh, I can say that, well, this is maybe because of lack of interest and lack of background information, uh, And, you know, some of the students neglect the class, the lecture. So, there are two reasons. Lack of interest, I mean negligence I mean, not paying attention to the subject and lack of grammar knowledge." (Teacher).

As a result of this negligence and low grammatical knowledge, the student does not make any progress and he/she cannot understand the received WCF codes. This is apart from creating obstacles for the students, it also makes problems for the teachers since the teacher has to repeatedly explain the codes and the structures with little or no benefit.

4.2.2.3 Time Constraints

The successful implementation of the revision requirement based on the teachers' provided WCF heavily depends on the time factor. To begin with, students need time to produce the first draft of their writing, then they need time to comprehend the provided WCF, and finally, they also need time to rewrite the whole passage and submit it to the teacher. This major reliance on time sometimes creates difficulties for the students and they cannot cope with the requirement within the confines of time as the teacher indicated that:

+ "15 minutes for reviewing, uh, was quite enough, but, uh, but concerning rewriting the

actual composition (in the revision stage), the whole composition, my students would ask for more time to finish their work. So, sometime, I would give them almost five more minutes to finish their work” (Teacher).

As it is apparent from the statement of the interviewed teacher, there will be times when teachers are obliged to extend the class time only to make it possible for their students to finish rewriting the task based on the provided WCF. When the time is not long enough, the students cannot rewrite the task and benefit from the revision process. As a result, they ask for more time to accomplish the task of rewriting which might not be feasible all the time for the teacher since there is a time limit for each class. As stated earlier, the class durations are limited, and teachers are obliged to end the session in the allocated time. This is reported by the expansion of the teacher in the following excerpt:

+ “well, as I said yes, my students would ask for extra time to finish the rewriting, but you know, although couple of times I was able to extend five more minutes of my class. However, this, like time extension was not applicable all the time because there are classes, I mean other classes after my session. That is why I couldn’t provide them with this extra time” (Teacher).

This issue of time constraints, as stated by the subject teacher in the above quote, is only confronted when the students rewrite the whole passage applying the teacher’s WCF, otherwise, it is not faced during the actual writing process.

Based on the three subthemes mentioned above, the low level of the students’ background knowledge, students’ negligence which led to re-submittal of the task without improvement and shortage of time can generate issues in the course of the revision process.

4.2.3 Theme Three: The Teacher’s Suggestions to Improve the Revision Practice

Revision can be a challenging procedure to practice, as outlined earlier, but it can be overcome with a few suggestions raised by the interviewed teacher. The interviewee has certain recommendations to overcome the challenges facing the revision process and to make it more beneficial for the students. These suggestions are outlined in the following three subthemes.

4.2.3.1 Providing Enough Explanation of the Codes and Grammatical Structures

The most critical step in improving the revision process is allocating more time for explaining the provided WCF codes and the grammatical structures to the students since all the self-corrections of the errors depend on understanding them. As was indicated earlier, if the student does not understand the provided WCF codes, there will be no revision and the whole process fails to be accomplished. Likewise, even if the students understand the codes, but do not have the background information about the correct form of the erroneous structure then the writing piece is resubmitted without any corrections and improvements. This suggestion is reported by the teacher in the subsequent extract:

+ “And another reason is pertinent to lack of information. Okay. So, um, how this issue can be solved in the future, in my opinion, the teacher might give more explanation about these grammatical mistakes and the codes that he uses in marking to the students to give more explanation about these things” (Teacher).

As such the teacher believes that before the start of the actual writing and the whole revision process, the instructor should allocate more time for explaining and practicing the grammatical structures which are in focus to pave the way for the student to fully acquire them. Once this is achieved, the teacher can initiate the implementation of the revision process. This is also evident in the teacher’s statement below:

+ “Also, by giving more practice to students, uh, about how to use, uh, these grammatical points so that they may be able to correct such mistakes when they are required to, to revise the writing” (Teacher).

This intensive practice facilitates automatization of the structure where the student is enabled to use this specific grammatical structure correctly all the time.

4.2.3.2 Providing Feedback on Other Aspects of Writing Other Than Grammatical Errors

Another suggestion that is brought up by the interviewee to enhance the impact of the revision practice is to provide WCF on the other aspects of writing and then require students to revise. In this study, the WCF is only directed towards locating grammatical accuracy and more specifically on three grammatical categories which are: Article system; subject-verb-

agreement; Verb form. It is believed that if the WCF is directed on the mechanics of writing too (not only the grammatical aspect), the impact on the accuracy of writing will be higher accordingly. The suggestion is to provide WCF on all writing aspects including grammar, lexis, syntax, discourse features, and mechanics of writing (punctuation and capitalization) (each separately). The interviewed teacher suggested the following:

+ “another suggestion that I might make is that in the future, uh, Teachers may focus on other matters, like, the structure of the composition, matters related to pre-writing how to act, to deal with the topics suggested whether it is specific enough or not, because when the topic is too general and students don't pay attention to this point by specifying it students find it difficult to begin to get started. Okay. So, if they go through a prewriting, go through steps of pre-writing by specifying the topic, if it is not, then by generating ideas about the specific topic through brainstorming and then, outlining for the idea that they get to and brainstorming, and when they see comments on the punctuation and spelling, I think. It is better in the future to focus on these matters too. so that the feedback and the revision might become more effective and successful” (Teacher).

The teacher also believes that the instructors, who require their students to revise, should include the steps of writing in their WCF, especially the pre-writing stage where the topic is properly selected, and adequate ideas are brainstormed. These all assist the learner to produce more accurate and fluent pieces of writing where revision can play a greater role.

4.2.3.3 Rewriting Only the Incorrect Sentences

One of the challenges that faces students during revision is the time limit because they are required to rewrite the whole passage after correction which can be solved by rewriting only the incorrect sentences. When the students are required to only rewrite these sentences which contain errors, this strategy will save them a large amount of time. This way the problem of not having enough time to rewrite is resolved. Another benefit of this strategy is not buying more time for the students only, it also motivates them better to continue with the revision practice since they do not have to rewrite long passages.

+ “Well, I suggest that in the future when we, as teachers, ask our students to revise the previous writing, I mean, not necessarily to ask our students to rewrite the whole composition. Okay. I think it's enough for students to rewrite only the sentences that contain

the mistakes because my students complained about Rewriting the whole composition when they would revise the mistakes” (Teacher).

Additionally, this suggestion helps the teacher avoid burnout because they do not have to reread the whole revised passage again, but only check the student's individual sentences to ensure that revisions have been made. This strategy solves the following problem stated by the teacher:

+ “Marking the tasks was time consuming, um this is true especially that some of the students, you know, had, I mean a very poor handwriting” (Teacher).

To summarize this theme, in order to overcome the challenges facing the revision practice and make it more effective some suggestions are there such as: Providing more explanation on the codes and grammatical structures; providing WCF on all aspects of writing (each in different tasks) rather than on a set of grammatical accuracy categories solely; and rewriting only the incorrect sentences not the whole writing to save more time and student energy.

In a nutshell, the whole interviews with the teacher indicated that demanding their students to revise is effective which makes the students have a positive attitude toward revision. Positive views increase the engagement and motivation of both students and teachers. However, some students might face difficulties in implementing teachers' comments due to their low level of grammatical background information which makes it difficult to understand the codes where they rewrite the text with no improvement, and they face time constraints as well. These problems can be overcome by following the teacher's suggestions to improve the revision practice such as providing enough explanation of the codes and grammatical structures, providing feedback on all aspects of writing, and rewriting only the incorrect sentences. The findings of both the quantitative and qualitative parts will be considered in more detail and discussed with reference to literature in the following section.

4.3 Discussion

There are messages to convey in writing pieces and to make the messages clear and intelligible, they must be free of grammatical errors. Therefore, it is beneficial for L2 writers to improve their grammatical accuracy to produce more accurate academic writing, enabling them to convey their ideas more effectively (Klimova, 2013). Teachers' WCFs can serve as clear guides that identify errors, their types, and the necessary corrections for students to turn their shortcomings into strengths. However, a lot of English teachers still regret the fact that their students do not even pay attention to the WCF that is provided, which deters teachers from continuing to employ it. Aiming to improve L2 students' grammatical accuracy and effectiveness of WCF, this study investigated if revision following WCF has an additive effect on the grammatical accuracy of Kurdish EFL learners as they receive low marks for their writing assignments (Ahmed, 2019), and it has been under-researched.

For proper comprehension of the effect of revision and to reply to the research questions, the data was initially collected through a quasi-experimental study in 14 weeks, where the students participated in five writing tasks. During this, the treatment group received the teacher's WCF for their written essays, and they were required to revise them, while the control group only reviewed the WCF feedback without revising. Then the researcher conducted a multi-session semi-structured interview with the subject teacher to gain his insights about the whole process of revision, to find out in which ways the revision was an (in)effective practice to improve the grammatical accuracy of students writing, and to what extent students were applying the comments in the revised versions. After that, the data from the quasi-experiment study was analysed through IBM SPSS, while the qualitative data was analysed through thematic analysis.

This section discusses the key findings with references to the literature. First of all, the efficacy of revision in improving L2 students' grammatical accuracy is discussed. Secondly, the researcher elaborates on whether revision plus WCF can have a long-term impact on grammatical accuracy, and whether the effect can be transferred to new pieces of writing. Then, the researcher discusses if practicing revision after receiving WCF can be more effective for certain grammatical features or if the impact will be the same. Finally, the light is shed on the evaluation of the teacher about the role of revision in students writing accuracy, and to what extent students were applying the comments in the revised versions.

4.3.1 The Impact of the Revision on Improving the Grammatical Accuracy of L2 Students' Writing

The quasi-experimental results demonstrated that there is a statistically significant effect of revision on students' academic writing. The immediate post-test revealed that students from the treatment group who revised their writings based on the teacher WCF performed statistically significantly better than control group students. This finding about the moderating effect of revision aligns with Ekanayaka and Ellis's (2020) finding. In their study, Ekanayaka and Ellis (2020) divided 91 students into three groups over a four-week period and had them write three tasks (WCF plus revision; WCF plus peer feedback; no WCF). Compared with the group without CF, the two groups that received WCF improved their accuracy. They also found that the revision group had the greatest gains in accuracy. On the other hand, contrary to the findings of the current study, the findings of two research conducted by Truscott and Hsu (2008), and Karim and Nassaji (2018) concluded that revision does not contribute to the learning of grammatical features. These two studies and their findings will be discussed later in the following section.

The positive effect of revision after WCF could be discussed by considering the fact that learning does not happen in a vacuum; that is why there should be appropriate context and means, including the provision of feedback to make the teaching materials and techniques work. The purpose behind the EFL/ESL teacher's provided feedback is to make learning happen and to fill in the gap in the linguistic knowledge of the students. The students need to work and act on the provided feedback to make the feedback successful and assist in L2 development. Based on what was found and experienced in this investigation, it could be discussed that the revision stage is exactly when learning happens because it is the time for applying the learned structure (Chandler, 2003). In other words, if the teacher's feedback is not followed by revision, there is a high possibility that the feedback will be of no or limited effect. This is even evident in the study conducted by Liu and Brown (2015), where they doubt the effect of WCF if the students are not requested to revise. Chandler (2003) goes even further to state that if there is no revision, the provided CF will have no effect. She concluded her study by claiming that "students did not revise their writing based on feedback about errors; having teachers mark errors was equivalent to giving no error feedback since the students' new writing did not increase in correctness over one semester" (p.280).

Additionally, the qualitative results revealed how and why revision can positively affect the grammatical accuracy of L2 learners. The results of the semi-structured interview explained that revision leads to a higher level of students' engagement in the writing process. According to Liu and Brown (2015), engaging students in the correction process by asking them to revise their texts based on the teacher's provided WCF is a powerful way to overcome students ignoring the provided CF. By taking responsibility for their writing, students will have more time to think, allowing them to better comprehend the correct form and frequency of errors. This can be made more reasonable when connected with the micro-cognitive process of learning when learning passes through the steps of noticing (comprehensible input), intake, internalization of the learned structure through practicing, and modified output (uptake) (Gass, 1997). When students make errors, this shows the mismatch between their interlanguage (IL) and the target-like structure (TLS). Once the teacher provides his/her WCF on these errors, this will act as explicit knowledge. This explicit knowledge, in return, will assist the students in cognitively processing the WCF input and learning from it.

Taking a further step, once teachers require their students to revise the texts through the provided WCF, this will assist them in being aware of the provided input and notice the structure. As a result, when students rewrite the text and produce the revised version after repairing and correcting their errors, they benefit from the feedback (Lyster & Ranta, 1997). According to the Noticing Hypothesis proposed by Schmidt (1995), only the noticed input becomes a learnt structure. In other words, the provided input (in this case, the WCF) is only learned when noticed, which is stimulated by the revision request.

Moreover, due to the fact that students are required to revise their text, before starting the rewriting, they need to understand the gap between the IL and the TLS. As stated earlier, this pushes them to notice and understand the provided input (in this case, the teacher's WCF). Based on Krashen's Monitor Model (Cook, 1993), when students are exposed to comprehensible input (learnt structure), this learnt structure acts as a monitor to provide modified output (the revised version), which in return facilitates L2 competence to increase. The reason is that the revising process provides the learner with enough time to access the learnt structure (which acts as a monitor here) and ponder upon the correct structure and modify it.

In addition to the benefits of revision highlighted above, the findings of the study also revealed that the actual revised version of the students, which is a modified product between students' hands, can be the subject of student attention. Since the revised version is the product that the students have provided after correcting their errors, they have the chance to look at the output they have produced and notice the correct forms. According to Swain's comprehensible output hypothesis (1985), only attending the input (WCF in this case) is not enough for improving grammatical knowledge and L2 competency, it is also necessary to notice the output (the revised version in this case). This is due to the reason that once students are demanded to produce target-like structures, this will enable them to observe the difference between their interlanguage and the target-like structure and accordingly identify the gap. The comprehensible output has been regarded as a complementary phase to the comprehensible input for urging students to produce target like grammatical structures needed for the academic writers (Donesch-Jezo, 2011).

The above explanations of the results of the study indicate that revision is a valuable resource in the process of L2 and L2 writing learning because students will take their steps in the process of L2 acquisition.

4.3.2 The Long-term Impact of Revision on Improving the Grammatical Accuracy of L2 Students' Writing

The previous section discussed how revision leads to improving the grammatical accuracy and correcting the incorrect structures, however, the most important query would be if this impact can be transferred over time to new pieces of writing. Therefore, now, I will move to the discussion of the second research question of the study about the possibility of revision's long-term impact on students' grammatical accuracy. The results of the delayed post-test, as compared to the results of the pre-test revealed that there is a statistically significant long-term effect of revision on students' grammatical accuracy improvement. Albeit the treatment group took the delayed post-test after two months of the interval from treatment, they still scored significantly higher than the control group, and they kept improving their grammatical accuracy. The results of this study indicate that students can improve their grammatical accuracy by revising their texts and that revising does produce benefits in new writing, as well as the ability to sustain these gains. This finding is in concordance with that of Chandler's (2003) study. She utilized an experimental design to test a total of 31 students

who are from East Asia (16 students in the control group and 15 students in the treatment group). In both groups, students wrote 25 pages of autobiographies over the semester. While the control group was not required to correct their errors throughout the semester, the treatment group was. Based on the results of her study, the treatment group's accuracy increased significantly compared to the control group. Accordingly, she concludes that this result refutes "the assertion that having students correct errors is ineffective" (2003, p. 279).

Nevertheless, the present finding, and Chandler's (2003) findings were different from Truscott and Hsu's (2008) and Karim and Nassaji's (2018) findings. Both of these studies found that the revision effect on grammatical accuracy does not pass to new pieces of writing, and it is not a long-term effect. Truscott and Hsu's (2008) study divided 47 ESL students into two groups (those who received WCF plus revision and those who received WCF without revision) at a Taiwanese public university. According to their findings, there was no correlation between success on the revision task and performance on a new writing task. In the same vein, Karim and Nassaji (2018) divided a total of 53 students into one direct, two indirect, and one control group. Students created three pieces of writing based on distinct photo prompts throughout a three-week period. Each group produced a second piece of writing two weeks later. All three feedback groups scored much better than the control group. Direct feedback improved accuracy in the near term, although the effects were largely insignificant. As such, the study found that there is no positive effect of revision on improving learners' grammatical accuracy in the long run.

However, these differences in the results can be explained reasonably since there are major differences between my study and these two studies. To begin with, Truscott and Hsu's (2008) study had only one-shot treatment which is not enough to lead to learning the grammatical structure. Ferris (1997) and Van Beuningen (2011) both state that since learning is an iterative process, to internalize the learned structure, it needs to be practiced over time. Furthermore, Li (2017) asserts that there should be multiple treatment sessions because "the more frequently one practice something, the more easily it is activated, the frequently it is used and the faster it is learnt" (De Bot et al., 2013, p. 210, as cited in Li, 2017, p. 138). As far as the current study is concerned, there were four treatment sessions which can explain why it has resulted in improving L2 learners' grammatical accuracy in new pieces of writing over time. Therefore, this study's findings suggest that teachers should create the chance of repetitious practices of the same targeted grammatical structures in

order to lead to student automatization. That is why teachers should not only explain the structure or only give one chance to the students to revise their writing and practice the targeted structure.

Another reason which has made the finding of this study different from Karim and Nassaji's (2018) is that they tested direct feedback plus revision not indirect feedback (since indirect feedback has been used in my study). According to Ferris (2004), indirect feedback is preferable to direct feedback since it encourages students to progress through problem-solving and uses more complex language processing. Although Karim and Nassaji (2018) participants said to be intermediate students, they themselves admitted that the placement tests "might not be fully accurate in terms of assessing language proficiency" (p. 18). They also acknowledged that the indirect feedback group was more advanced in their language proficiency as compared to the direct feedback group which is why there was less room for improvement as such their pre-test and post-test scores did not differ significantly. This indicates an issue in the experimental study they have conducted as the groups before the start of the treatment were not equal which cannot provide reliable results. This explanation of the finding of the current study and the other two studies with different findings recommends that teachers should take into consideration the language proficiency level of their students to decide on the type of feedback.

The third difference between the current and the other two studies' finding was because of the scope of the provided feedback; the current study used focused feedback (feedback on a single or a few errors) while the other two studies provided comprehensive feedback (i.e., feedback on all errors). According to Van Beuningen (2011), providing comprehensive feedback makes students feel overwhelmed and disrupts their feedback processing, whereas giving focused feedback makes them more aware of grammatical errors. Karim and Nassaji (2018) also admit that the most impact of feedback and revision was on the grammatical errors compared to the non-grammatical errors (because their feedback range included both error types unlike the current study which only focused on three grammatical errors). Furthermore, the contrast between treatable and untreatable errors may aid in understanding this. Treatable errors are those errors that are rule-patterned such as article system, regular past tense, and other grammatical errors. According to Ferris (2009), feedback would be more successful when it targets grammatical (treatable) errors rather than untreatable errors which do not have an underlying rule to be

corrected. As such, the current study proposes that teachers' provided feedback needs to be selective and focused on a small range of grammatical errors to allow students process them, understand them, and then learn them.

These differences and their explanations prove that for revision to be successful, the provided feedback should be indirect, focused feedback, and the treatment should be multiple sessions to provide enough space for practice.

4.3.3 Various Types of Grammatical Features are Impacted Differently by Revision Followed by WCF

Testing the impact of WCF followed by revision on a single grammatical error might not provide accurate results since, as stated earlier there are different error types that require different CF types. Although many of the previous studies have examined the impact of WCF on single error types (e.g., Bitchener & Knoch, 2009; Ellis et al., 2008; Frear, 2012; Shintani & Ellis, 2013), the current study investigated the effect of revision following WCF on multiple grammatical error types (Article system (AS), subject-verb-agreement (SVA), and verb form (VF)). Thus, this section deals with discussing the findings related to the third research question of the study which was "How does revision affect different types of grammatical aspects of L2 students' writing?".

The quasi-experimental results demonstrated that there is a statistically significant different effect of revision on various types of grammatical features of students' academic writing. The results revealed that the most impact of revision has been on AS ($m=15.23$) and then on SVA ($m=4.88$) while the least effect of revision has been on VF ($m=1.48$). These findings are in line with the results of Bitchener et al. (2005). They investigated the impact of WCF on three grammatical errors: prepositions, past simple tense, and definite article. They divided 53 post-intermediate ESL students into control and treatment groups. They found that WCF impact was different on each grammatical error in a way that students' accuracy increased significantly in using the past simple tense and definite article while it did not in using prepositions. More interestingly, even in the past simple tense, the students' accuracy better increased in using regular verbs than irregular verbs. In the same vein, Dabboub (2019) presented the same results (students' verb errors were better improved as compared to the prepositions) where she carried out an experimental study at a university

in Libya with 60 English language first-year students. Moreover, in my study, the verb forms were the least impacted by WCF because a big part of the students' errors was in the irregular verb forms, that is why it has been the least impacted by WCF. This brings about a valid explanation why the current study found different effects of WCF on different error types. This means that we again need to refer back to the distinction between treatable and untreatable errors, since the irregular past tense is not rule governed as such it falls under untreatable errors while regular past tense follows an underlying rule thus belongs to treatable errors. This explanation may clarify the reason why prepositions and irregular past tense did not improve (as they fall under untreatable errors) while regular past simple tense did (Ferris, 1999).

According to Ferris (2006), direct WCF is more helpful for errors that are "untreatable" i.e., errors where students might not be able to correct themselves because "there are no specific rules", while indirect WCF is beneficial for "treatable errors"; "errors that students may be able to self-correct, and which have specific rules" (p.9). With that being discussed, it becomes evident that the type of the provided CF (direct or indirect) plays different roles on the different error types. In my study, indirect WCF was provided that is why the impact was more prominent on the treatable errors rather on untreatable errors. These findings assist the teachers to choose their WCF type more accurately where if they intent to work on the rule-governed errors, they should provide indirect CF. On the other hand, if the focus is on untreatable errors where there are no underlying rules, it will be more beneficial if the teacher provides direct WCF.

Different revision effects on the various grammatical features of L2 students' writing in the current study can also be explained with reference to Krashen's natural order hypothesis of acquisition. According to Krashen (2018), grammatical structures are acquired in a "predetermined, natural order" in which some features are acquired earlier than others (p.13). As previously stated, the current study found that the English article system is the most improved and the verb form is the least improved. This is in accordance with Krashen's (2018) natural order of acquisition table 2.1, which points out that articles are acquired earlier than verb forms. Further, the table shows that, even between regular and irregular past verbs, regular past verbs are acquired earlier (Krashen, 2018, p. 13). These findings provide instructors with hints about how to teach different grammar structures as Krashen (2018) points out "...It seems reasonable that we should present rules one at a time in some

order when the goal is conscious learning" (p. 122). Nevertheless, he further states that the findings of the natural order hypothesis should not always be used as the basis for teaching grammatical features. This is due to the reason that while planning curricula to teach different grammatical structures, other factors must be considered, including frequency of occurrence and linguistic simplicity.

Moving forward, the following section discusses the perceptions and reflections of teachers and students received during the implementations of the revision practice.

4.3.4 The Implementation of Revision Following WCF Creates Different Reactions and Consequences

The application of revision practice is not a simple task to be achieved as there are some factors and challenges (the teacher's and students' reactions, classroom time limit, learners' background knowledge and their motivation level) which need to be taken into consideration that may affect the effectiveness of the process. This section discusses the answer to the fourth research question of the study which was "What is the perception of teachers towards the process and effect of revision on students' writing?". The results of the teacher's interviews made it apparent that demanding students to revise leads to a more positive attitude towards revision. Students and teachers are more likely to engage and be motivated when they have positive views toward the procedure of the classes. The findings of the current study were contrary to the study by Yu et al. (2020). They investigated the impact of students' attitudes on motivation and engagement in WCF on L2 writing through a comprehensive L2 writing feedback scale applied on 1190 English majored students at 35 universities in China. They found that the students generally had a negative attitude towards WCF consequently they were demotivated, and they did not want to get engaged with more WCF. As I stated earlier, however, my study found that students had a positive view of revision and WCF, resulting in an increased motivation level and better engagement. This difference in the results of these two studies might be due to the fact that different types of CF have been provided to the students (indirect focused feedback in my study but direct comprehensive feedback in the other study). Yu et al. (2020) also acknowledged that giving students direct, comprehensive WCF had led to low self-esteem in the students, which caused them to shift to failure avoidance techniques including not applying WCF in their writing tasks as a way to avoid failure. The large amount of provided WCF has overwhelmed

them and created a heavy burden on them as such they have been demotivated and avoided more practices. On the other hand, the researchers themselves concluded the study by stating that their research “yields empirical support for a focused and selective approach to WCF as this could foster a stronger sense of control and valuing when students engage with L2 writing” (2020, p.13) which is the case in my study.

Learning progress and goal achievement can be monitored and assessed with revision and WCF, which contributes to the development of self-regulated learning and a sense of accomplishment. When learners become responsible for their correction as they are self-regulated, they develop a sense of completion which in return makes them have positive attitudes towards this practice and be highly motivated to carry on with it. According to Hummel (2014), attitudes and motivation are closely tied to persistence and success in L2 learning. These results show that as the students are highly engaged in the task of revision, their attitude is positive towards it, and they are also motivated to observe their ideal L2 self. Furthermore, the gained motivation relieves stress and anxiety, preventing the student from developing the proposed affective filter that blocks language acquisition. The affective filter hypothesis is proposed by Krashen (1985, as cited in Cook, 1993), in which he says that stress and anxiety act as a barrier and filter in front of language acquisition devices that prevent input from crossing it. This barrier, as stated earlier, is resolved by asking students to revise their texts based on the teacher’s feedback since their motivation level is increased.

Additionally, according to Ellis (2010), learner engagement can be interpreted from three perspectives: cognitive engagement “how learners attend to the CF they receive”, behavioural engagement which is related to output or the revision of the text, and attitudinal engagement which is associated with learners’ positive or negative attitude towards the practice (p. 342). Based on the current study's findings, these interpretations of learner engagement can be achieved from revision following WCF as the students have been engaged in correcting their errors to provide revised versions, which has increased their motivation level to attend the forms. Therefore, it can be stated that the positive attitude and high motivational level gained from this practice can lead to and be interpreted as a key to learners’ deep engagement with WCF. As Ellis (2010) points out, such engagement makes students responsible for their own learning rather than passive receivers.

In addition to raising students' motivation levels, the current study also revealed that revision motivates teachers to provide WCF. The revising process serves as a formative assessment of learners' writings because it informs the teacher about the extent of students' improvement from the CF, the extent to which the provided type of CF was successful, and assures the teacher that students are working on the feedback. Teachers will be able to see from the revised versions that extensive time spent correcting students' papers has not been wasted. Najmaddin (2010) conducted a study at the Koya university in the Kurdistan region of Iraq that supports these findings. Through interviews and reflection journals, she explored the views of nine English language teachers about WCF types. It was found that teachers were motivated to provide feedback when they provided the right type of feedback since they paid attention to the students' level to ensure that the feedback type was appropriate for them. In this study, however, the students were not required to revise, which made it difficult for them to determine whether the feedback was appropriate as compared to their language proficiency level. As a result of the requirement for learners to revise, my study will involve continuous assessment of the students so that the teacher can measure the effectiveness of the feedback regularly.

Additionally, the current study yielded different results, beyond the fact that revision increases student engagement and motivation, nevertheless, it can be challenging to apply it to the classroom. There are several factors which may create problems for the teachers while requiring their students to revise their texts inside the classroom. These problems are the low level of the students' background knowledge, students' negligence and lack of interest, re-submittal of the task without improvement and shortage of time. It is worth mentioning that these difficulties were experienced by a few students while the rest did not have these issues.

To begin with, a small number of students, due to their low level of grammatical knowledge, were incapable of understanding the coded feedback and were unable to figure out the correct forms themselves and consequently could not revise their texts. This is one of the challenges of providing indirect feedback because the students have to self-correct themselves. As such, once their level of grammatical background information is low, they cannot revise their texts. As stated earlier, although this was the case with a small number of students, still their proficiency level needs to be accurately determined by the teacher so that the most effective type of feedback is provided. This issue of students not being able

to respond to the provided WCF was also brought up by Truscott (1996) as one of the reasons why grammar correction is problematic. He argued that it is not easy for students to understand the feedback provided by the teacher as such incapable of benefiting from it. Najmaddin (2010) also emphasized this clearly, stating that when selecting the appropriate WCF type for her students, the teachers had to pay extra attention to the students' language proficiency levels. In light of these findings, teachers should pay particular attention to evaluating learners' proficiency levels before making a decision about the type of feedback they should provide.

According to the qualitative results of the study, other issues facing the implementation of revision practice included time shortages during the revision process, leading to students asking for more time. These findings are in agreement with those of Polio et al (1998). Researchers tested 65 ESL students at Michigan State University for a period of seven weeks to see if revision and feedback reduced sentence-level errors in essays. They found that although students benefited from the revision practice, they asked for more time to finish the revised tasks. However, although a small number of participants were affected by this problem, the suggestion from the interviewed teacher can still resolve this issue. In order to ensure that the students will be able to manage their time and benefit from the feedback, the suggestion is to ask them to rewrite only the incorrect sentences, not the whole passage.

In a nutshell, demanding students to revise leads to a more positive attitude towards revision. Students and teachers are more likely to engage and be motivated when they have positive views. In addition to raising students' motivation levels, the current study also revealed that revision motivates teachers to provide WCF as well. Beyond the fact that revision increases student engagement and motivation, nevertheless, it can be challenging to apply it to the classroom. These challenges are the low level of the students' background knowledge, rewriting the task without improvement, and shortage of time. These can be related to and solved through the appropriate type of feedback in relation to considering students' proficiency level. Also, to ensure that the students are able to manage their time and benefit from the feedback, teachers should ask them to rewrite only the incorrect sentences, not the whole passage.

Chapter 5: Conclusions

Writing has recently received more attention in Second Language Acquisition (SLA) due to the importance it plays in assessing the learning, work, and intellect of Second Language (L2) users as well as assisting students in communicating their messages and ideas more effectively. However, learning to write proficiently is challenging since extensive instruction and training are required. The Kurdistan Region of Iraq has many EFL university students who struggle with their writing tasks and want to improve, but they are unsure of where the issues lie and how to address them. Many students struggle to process the input they receive during writing classes in order to convert it to uptake and contribute to their L2 acquisition. An effective practical solution to this is the provision of corrective feedback (CF), where students need to take care of the input. Despite the fact that many teachers provide WCF to their students in Kurdistan Region of Iraq (KRI) tertiary contexts, few of them are well-equipped with a systematic method for providing. Moreover, even once CF is provided, many students do not pay attention to it and ignore it, thereby demotivating teachers to continue providing WCF to their students. It is therefore necessary to ask students to revise their writings to make the provided CF more effective in L2 writing learning. Thus, the purpose of the current study is to examine whether revision following WCF can improve students' writing accuracy and whether this effect can be transferred to new writing pieces. Additionally, it considers whether the revision is equally influential on different types of grammatical features (Article System, Subject-Verb-Agreement, and Verb Form). It further explores the perception of the teacher towards the process of revision and its effect on students' writing performance. Consequently, this study provides clear insights into the practicality and usefulness of WCF and revision to teachers struggling to improve their students' writing abilities. It also guides teachers about the mechanism of implementing WCF and asking their students to revise their writing. In addition, students will be able to identify their errors and deficiencies in order to improve their writing proficiency and accuracy.

Since this study sought to find out how revision influences L2 students' grammatical accuracy, it was crucial to observe the process of revision following WCF in the classroom. I used a mixed method approach for data collection and analysis. The quantitative data were collected using a quasi-experimental design in which 50 second-year English students from an Iraqi Kurdistan Region public university served as treatment and control groups. A total

of five essays of two hundred words were to be written by each student. Initially, the control group was asked to simply review the teacher's feedback without revising. However, the treatment group was required to revise and rewrite their writings in response to feedback. Qualitative data were collected through a semi-structured interview with the subject teacher following the treatment. An analysis of the quantitative data was performed using SPSS, while a thematic analysis was carried out on the qualitative data.

The findings of the study indicated that students could improve their grammatical accuracy by revising their texts and that revising does produce benefits in new writings, as well as the ability to sustain these gains. This study's findings suggested that teachers should create repeated opportunities for students to practice the same targeted grammatical structures in order to lead to student automatization (see section 4.3.2). Moreover, it proved that the effect of revision varies from one grammatical feature to another. The results revealed that the most impact of revision is on AS and then on SVA while the least effect of revision is on VF. Part of the VF is irregular past tense which falls under the untreatable errors category. In the current study, indirect WCF was used following revision to treat grammatical errors, which according to the findings of the current study and previous literature is more beneficial for "treatable errors" than for "untreatable errors".

The findings further suggested that demanding students to revise leads to a more positive attitude towards revision and this positive view leads students and teachers to be engaged and motivated. In addition to raising students' motivation levels, the current study also revealed that revision motivates teachers to provide WCF as well. It was also found that beyond the fact that revision increases student engagement and motivation, nevertheless, it can be challenging to apply it to the classroom. Among these challenges are students' little background knowledge, rewriting the task without improving it, and a shortage of time. However, by providing the appropriate type of feedback that considers the proficiency level of the students, these issues can be identified and solved. Also, to ensure that students are able to manage their time and benefit from feedback, teachers should ask them to rewrite only the incorrect sentences, not the whole passage.

Finally, the findings indicate that two factors should be considered in order to improve the writing accuracy of L2 students. As a first step toward making revision and CF provision successful, teachers are recommended to consider their students' language proficiency

level when choosing feedback types. Secondly, teachers' provided feedback needs to be selective and focused on a small range of grammatical errors to allow students to process them, understand them, and then learn from them.

5.1 Implications

A number of regional and international companies, institutions, and businesses have taken notice of Kurdistan in the recent past. A constant demand is made by these associations to hire qualified and competent staff. Applicants for such positions must be proficient English speakers and writers. As a result, candidates who are good at writing have a better chance of being hired by these companies. Despite being proficient in English speaking, many EFL students and graduates complain that they have poor writing skills. This negatively affects students' performance on academic tests and their prospects of getting hired. Even though many teachers teach writing courses at the tertiary level in KRI and provide students with WCF, students still struggle to identify their shortcomings and improve their L2 writing skills. There might be two possible explanations for this, either a problem with the provided feedback system or a failure on the part of the students to comprehend the feedback.

As a result, this thesis explored the add-on effect of revision method as an alternative solution to this problem, and the findings turned out to be promising. In addition to improving their writing skills, English language students will have better chances of finding a job after graduation or pursuing graduate studies. Using the results of this study, teachers may be able to pick their WCF type more accurately, and if they want to work on rule-governed errors, they may provide indirect corrections. Conversely, if the focus is on untreatable errors with no underlying rules, direct WCF would be more beneficial (see sections 4.3.2 & 4.3.4). As a result of the findings, teachers must decide on the type of feedback based on the level of their students' language proficiency. In order to improve the grammar accuracy of the L2 students, it is more effective to provide indirect feedback if the students are at least intermediate level. It is also recommended that teachers provide students with repeated practice of targeted grammatical structures to facilitate student automatization of learning new L2 structures. It is, therefore, imperative that teachers do not only explain the structure to students or give them only one chance to practice it.

In this way, students, teachers, curriculum designers, and policy makers as a whole

could benefit from the results, which could support learning environments as a whole in improving L2 students' writing accuracy. Furthermore, this will help the ministry of higher education provide guidelines for teachers and train them regarding the aforementioned points so that their students can become proficient writers. Finally, the results encourage all the mentioned stakeholders to incorporate revision and WCF into the education system so as to equip learners for today's marketplace.

5.2 Limitations and Recommendations for Future Research

This study had a number of limitations. To begin with, the study interviewed only one writing teacher in order to examine his perception of the challenges and mechanisms associated with implementing the revision requirement. This was due to the fact that there are few instructors who require their students to revise their writing in the KRI context, as such, other writing teachers who did not require their students to revise were not included in the qualitative data collection. Another limitation is that this study only examined how revision following WCF improved L2 students' grammatical errors, whereas this effect needs to be explored in terms of other writing aspects, especially the mechanics of writing such as the structure and organization of academic writing as it assists learners in becoming academic writers. Moreover, the number of students in each of the treatment and the control groups was originally 64 (32 each), but due to a high mortality rate, the number was reduced to 50 (25 in each group). Although 50 is a decent sample size and the experiment had a substantial effect size, it would be more useful to do the research with a larger group of students to ensure that the results are more generalizable. These limitations reduce the extent to which the present findings can be generalised.

As a result, the recommendations for further studies can be summarized as follows; It is necessary to conduct more empirical studies in this area since this is the first attempt in the KRI context and one of the few studies conducted globally. For the qualitative part, we need to engage more writing instructors to gain a deeper understanding of the mechanism of implementing revision practices and the challenges they face. Additionally, since, in the current study students were not interviewed about the issues and challenges they encountered during the process, as such more in-depth, and longitudinal qualitative studies are needed by interviewing students on their reflections and difficulties they encountered during the revision requirement.

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Appendix 1

University of Kurdistan-Hawler
School of Social Sciences
English Language Department
Erbil
Phone Number: 00964(0)750 430 3927

PARTICIPANT INFORMATION SHEET FOR INSTITUTIONS

Title: The Effect of Revision Following Teacher's Indirect Written Corrective Feedback on Learners' L2 Grammatical Accuracy in EFL Writing Classes

To: Head of Department

My name is Rebaz Yaseen Abbas. I am a master's degree student within the Department of English Language/ Applied Language and TESOL Program at University of Kurdistan-Hawler. My major is language teaching. Part of the requirements of my degree is that I undertake research related to language teaching. In particular, I am interested in writing tasks. The research is longitudinal in that it will be conducted in seven sessions over a fourteen-week period. Therefore, I need the assistance of one English language teacher and some English language students so as to conduct my research. As such, I would like to invite some to participate in this research.

Please could you give permission to access students on site.

What follows is a brief description of the anticipated implementation of the research covering seven sessions of approximately two hour each over 14 weeks. The process will take 14 weeks where students receive feedback on their written assignments then they will submit their revised version of papers

Later, the Instructor will be interviewed about their perceptions about the process.

The background questionnaire will take about fifteen minutes, the writing tasks about 45 minutes each, working on the writing tasks about 30 minutes each, and the interview will take about 20 minutes each.

Please note that names of particular language learners and their individual results will NOT be included in the thesis

Due to the voluntary nature of the participation in the research, I would like to seek your assurance that students' or teachers' participation or non-participation will not affect the student or teachers' relationship with the school or the grades of the students.

Moreover, if the institution decides that it does not want to participate in the research, it may withdraw at any time before and during the research and up to three weeks after the completion of the research.

If you would like further information about this project, please feel free to contact me through my contact details below.

Rebaz Yaseen Abbas
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Dr. Zana Ibrahim (Head of Department)
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Salahadin University
College of languages
Erbil
Phone Number: 00964(0)7504453971

Department of English Language

**CONSENT FORM FOR INSTITUTIONS
THIS CONSENT FORM WILL BE HELD FOR A PERIOD OF SIX YEARS**

Title: The Effect of Revision Following Teacher's Indirect Written Corrective Feedback on Learners' L2 Grammatical Accuracy in EFL Writing Classes

Researcher: Rebaz Yaseen Abbas

From: Head of Department

The project has been explained to me and I understand what I have been told. I have had an opportunity to ask questions and have them answered.

- I agree to the researcher using the results of one background questionnaire, five writing tasks, written feedback and revision of writing tasks.
- I understand that the research will be conducted in seven sessions. The questionnaire will take about 15 minutes, the writing tasks about 45 minutes each, working on the writing tasks about 30 minutes each and the interview will take about 20 minutes each.
- I understand that the writing tasks will be designed expressly for the sake of research, they have no direct relationship to the routine part of the teaching cycle and that students can receive feedback on their performance after the completion of the research if they request it.
- I understand that the institution can withdraw its participation at any time before and during the research and up to three weeks after its completion.
- I understand that students' names will not be used in the final report on this project, so no one will know who the students are or their performance on the writing tasks.
- I affirm that participation or non-participation will not affect the students or teachers' relationship with the school or the grades of the students. I understand that the institution is under no obligation to participate in this project.
- I understand that students may withdraw their data from this project at any time without giving a reason, and that they will be informed accordingly.

Signed: _____

Name: *Asst. Prof. Dr. Lanja Abdul rozay Dababgh*
Position: *Acting Head of the English Department*
Name of Institution: *SUH, College of Languages*
Date: *1.2.2022*

Appendix 2

University of Kurdistan-Hawler
School of Social Sciences
English Language Department
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Phone Number: 00964(0)750 430 3927

PARTICIPANT INFORMATION SHEET FOR INSTITUTIONS

Title: The Effect of Revision Following Teacher's Indirect Written Corrective Feedback on Learners' L2 Grammatical Accuracy in EFL Writing Classes

To: Teacher

My name is Rebaz Yaseen Abbas. I am a Master Degree student within the Department of English Language/Applied Language and TESOL program at University of Kurdistan-Hawler. My major is language teaching. Part of the requirements of my degree is that I undertake research related to language teaching. In particular, I am interested in writing tasks. The research is longitudinal in that it will be conducted in five sessions over a five-week period. Therefore, I need the assistance of one English language teacher and some English language students so as to conduct my research. As such, I would like to invite you to participate in this research.

What do you do?

You will implement a number of procedures within five episodes of data collection – one per week for four weeks and one 8 weeks later. Each episode will take approximately 45 minutes to one hour of class time. Prior to the data collection I, the researcher, will outline the procedures for collecting the data which involve the following. Week one will involve the students completing a background questionnaire and writing task 1. You will take writing task 1 away and write some feedback on the students' writing. In week two, the students will first work with the feedback from writing task 1 and then revise this writing task and submit it to you, after that, they do writing task 2. You will take writing task 2 away and write some feedback on the students' writing. For week three, the students will work on the feedback from writing task 2 and then revise this writing task and submit it to you, after that, they do writing task 3. You will take writing task 3 away and write some feedback on the students' writing. For week four, the students will work on the feedback from writing task 3 and then revise this writing task and submit it to the instructor. A number of weeks later students will write task 4 and submit it to you.

Later, the Instructor will be interviewed about their perceptions about the process.

The questionnaire will take about 15 minutes, the writing tasks about 45 minutes each, working on the writing tasks about 30 minutes each, and the interview will take about 20 minutes each

What will the researcher do with the information collected during the classes?

Firstly, each participant and their relevant information will be assigned a number so that anonymity can be maintained. The information from the background questionnaire and the writing

tasks will be analyzed and form the basis of a MA thesis to be presented to University of Kurdistan-Hawler. You may see a copy of the thesis upon its completion.

You may request to have some feedback on the instructional procedure upon the completion of the research. Feedback from the researcher prior to this would bias the results of the research.

Due to the voluntary nature of the participation in the research, I would like to seek your assurance that students' participation or non-participation will not affect the students' relationship with the school or their grades.

If you decide that you do not want to participate in the research, you may withdraw it at any time before and during the research and up to three weeks after the completion of the research. You are under no obligation to allow the data to be used.

Thank you for considering participating in this research.

If you would like further information about this project, please feel free to contact me through my contact details below.

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Department of English Language

CONSENT FORM FOR INSTITUTIONS
THIS CONSENT FORM WILL BE HELD FOR A PERIOD OF SIX YEARS

Title: The Effect of Revision Following Teacher's Indirect Written Corrective Feedback on Learners' L2 Grammatical Accuracy in EFL Writing Classes

Researcher: Rebaz Yaseen Abbas

From: The Teacher

The project has been explained to me and I understand what I have been told. I have had an opportunity to ask questions and have them answered.

- I agree to the researcher using the results of the background questionnaire, five writing tasks, written feedback and revision of writing tasks.
- I understand that the research will be conducted in seven sessions. The questionnaire will take about 15 minutes, the writing tasks about 45 minutes each, working on the writing tasks about 30 minutes each and the interview will take about 20 minutes each.
- I understand that the writing tasks will be designed expressly for the sake of research, they have no direct relationship to the routine part of the teaching cycle and that students can receive feedback on their performance after the completion of the research if they request it.
- I understand that the institution can withdraw its participation at any time before and during the research and up to three weeks after its completion.
- I understand that students' names will not be used in the final report on this project, so no one will know who the students are or their performance on the writing tasks.
- I affirm that participation or non-participation will not affect the students or teachers' relationship with the school or the grades of the students. I understand that the institution is under no obligation to participate in this project.
- I understand that students may withdraw their data from this project at any time without
- I understand that students may withdraw their data from this project at any time without giving a reason, and that they will be informed accordingly.

Signed: _____

Name:

Position:

Name of Institution:

Date:

SALAM MOHAMMED KARIM
Assistant Lecturer
Salahaddin University - College of
Languages - English Department
1/2/2022

Appendix 3

Background Questionnaire

Student Name: _____ Group: _____

Stage: _____

1. How old are you? _____

2. Are you male or female? _____

3. What was your average in High school (12th Grade)? _____

4. What was your mark in English in the Final exam in High school (12th Grade)? _____

5. How many years have you been studying English? _____

6. Have you previously taken any of English Language Tests such as IELTS, TOEFL or PTE? YES NO

If YES, what was your score? _____

Appendix 4

Loyal Friendship → *

We have many type of friendship, there are good and bad

side. the best one is loyal friendship. ^{SVA} friendship like

a sea that you can fill it with loyalty, love, happiness. Some time

this friendship between two ^P ^{SVA} ^F friend make them feel that they can't

leave without each other.

First of all, loyalty between two friend make them feel

comfortable and feel that there are ^{SVA} someone who can share his or

her happiness or sadness. they can tell each other their secret that

make them feel comfortable. although some time it is not ^{AS} good thing.

the second advantage of loyal friendship is for society that

educate a person who ^{SVA} ^F know how to respect and protect the secret

between them.

the third advantage in loyal friendship in university or

school they can share their information with each other

and study with each other, and not waste their time.

thing is that friendship is very nice with loyalty, that

make them feel comfortable, happy, ^{and} protect their secret and share their information.

In order to conclude my speech, friendship is very nice if friends

know how to respect each other and achieve the trust with each

other, because some time they lost this trust ^{VF} in addition they feel

lonely and sad

* ~~friendship is relationship between two friend that fill with loyalty.~~

and study with each other, and not waste their time.

thing is that friendship is very nice with loyalty, that make them feel comfortable, happy, and protect their secret and share their information.

In order to conclude my speech, friendship is very nice. If friends know how to respect each other and achieve the trust with each other, because some time they lost this trust in addition they feel lonely and sad.

* ~~friendship is relationship between two friend that fill with loyalty.~~

$$\left. \begin{array}{l} AS \frac{4}{5} = 80 \\ SVA \frac{31}{35} = 88.5 \\ VF \frac{33}{35} = 94.5 \end{array} \right\} = 87.6$$

Appendix 5

Review

Shokhan abdulKarim

Loyal Friendship

We have many types of friendship. There are good and

bad side. The best one is loyal friendship. Friendship is

like a sea that you can fill it with loyalty, love, happiness,

Sometimes this friendship between two friends make them

feel that they can't live without each other.

First of all, loyalty between two friends make them feel

comfortable and feel that there is someone who can share

his or her happiness or sadness. They can tell each other their

secret, that make them feel comfortable, although sometimes

it is not a good thing.

The second advantage of loyal friendship is for society

educates a person who knew how to respect and protect

the secret between them.

The third advantage in loyal friendship in university or school they can share their information with each other and study with each other, and ^{not} waste their time.

The last thing is that, friendship is very nice with loyalty that makes them feel comfortable, happy, and protect their secret and share their information.

In order to conclude my speech, friendship is very nice if friends know how to respect each other and achieve the trust with other, because sometimes they lose trust, in addition they feel lonely and sad.

Appendix 6

Interview Questions

1. What was the reflection and the reaction of your students to submit the revised version of their written assignment?
2. Were students able to implement your comments in the revised version of their writing assignments?
3. In which aspects of grammatical accuracy did students have difficulty to understand your comments and apply it in their revised version?
4. Was the time sufficient to conduct the, the actual writing task, the review and revision?
5. What challenges did you face while conducting the required activities during the explanation of the task, asking students to write, correcting their writing, asking students to revise and collection the task?
6. What sort of suggestion would you like to give to make the feedback and the revision more effective and successful?

Abstract - Arabic خلاصة

غالبًا ما يقدم معلمو اللغة الإنجليزية كلفةً أجنبيةً ملاحظات تصحيحية مكتوبة نظرًا لمساهمتها في تطوير الكتابة باللغة الثانية. ومع ذلك ، فإن العديد من الطلاب لا يأخذون التعليقات التصحيحية الكتابية المقدمة في الاعتبار. وفقًا لذلك ، يعتقد بعض الباحثين أن التعليقات التصحيحية المكتوبة جنبًا إلى جنب مع المراجعة قد تشرك الطلاب في عملية تصحيح الأخطاء وتجعل الملاحظات المقدمة أكثر فعالية. على الرغم من أن العديد من الدراسات قد فحصت فعالية التعليقات التصحيحية المكتوبة ، فإن مساهماتها في دور الوسيط للمراجعة ضئيلة وغير حاسمة بسبب القيود المنهجية أو التصميمية ولم يتم إجراء أي دراسات حول هذا الموضوع في إقليم كردستان العراق. لذلك ، تفحص الدراسة الحالية تأثير المراجعة التي تتبع الملاحظات التصحيحية المكتوبة على تحسين دقة الكتابة للطلاب الأكراد في اللغة الإنجليزية وما إذا كان يمكن نقل هذا التأثير إلى قطع كتابية جديدة. علاوة على ذلك ، فإنه يحقق في ما إذا كانت الأنواع المختلفة من السمات النحوية (نظام التعريف ، واتفاق فعل والفاعل ، وصيغة الفعل) تتأثر بالتساوي بممارسة المراجعة. كما يستكشف تصور المعلم المادة تجاه عملية المراجعة وتأثيرها على أداء الكتابة لدى الطلاب. لتحقيق هذه الأهداف ، استخدمت الدراسة تصميمًا متعدد الأساليب لجمع البيانات وتحليلها. تم جمع البيانات الكمية باستخدام تصميم شبه تجريبي تم فيه تعيين 50 طالبًا إنجليزيًا في السنة الثانية من إحدى الجامعات الحكومية في إقليم كردستان العراق كعلاج (تمت مراجعة كتاباتهم بناءً على الملاحظات التصحيحية المكتوبة) ومجموعات المراقبة (تم التحقق فقط من التعليقات التصحيحية المكتوبة بدون مراجعة كتاباتهم). بعد العلاج ، أجريت مقابلة شبه منظمة مع مدرس المادة لتأمين البيانات النوعية. تم تحليل البيانات باستخدام برنامج SPSS والتحليل الموضوعي. أظهرت نتائج المرحلة الكمية أن مراجعة مهام الكتابة تعزز الدقة النحوية في الكتابة اللغوية الثانية وتأثيرها مستمر في قطع الكتابة الجديدة بمرور الوقت. ومن النتائج الأخرى أن مستوى تأثير المراجعة يختلف من سمة نحوية إلى أخرى. فيما يتعلق بذلك ، تم الاستنتاج أيضًا من البيانات النوعية أن مطالبة الطلاب بمراجعتها فعالة في تعزيز المشاركة والتحفيز لكل من الطلاب والمعلمين. تساهم هذه الدراسة في رفع مستوى الوعي بين أصحاب المصلحة حول كيفية دمج واستخدام الملاحظات التصحيحية الكتابية والمراجعة في العملية التعليمية.

الكلمات المفتاحية: ردود الفعل التصحيحية الكتابية ، المراجعة ، الدقة النحوية ، المدرسون ، الطلاب.

Abstract - Kurdish پوختە

مامۆستایانی زمانی ئینگلیزی وەک زمانیکى بیانی زۆر جار بەهۆی بەشداریکردنی له پەرەپێدانی نووسینی زمانی دووهەمدا، فیدبایکی چاکسازی نووسراو پیشکش دەکەن. بەلام زۆریک له خوێندکاران ئەو فیدبایە چاکسازییە نووسراوانەى که پیشکش کراوه له بەرچاواناگر. بەم پێیە، هەندیک له توێژەران پێیان وایە که فیدبای چاکسازی نووسراو له گەڵ پێداچوونەوهدا رەنگه خوێندکاران له پرۆسەى راستکردنەوهی هەلەکاندا بەشدار بکەن و فیدبایەکانی پیشکشکراو کاربەگەرتر بکەن. هەرچەندە زۆریک له لیکۆئێنەوهکان کاربەگەری فیدبای چاکسازی نووسراویان تاوتوێ کردووه، بەلام بەشدارییەکانیان له رۆتی نیوەندگیزی پێداچوونەوهدا کهمترین و بێ ئەنجامه بەهۆی سنوورداریبوونی میتۆدۆلۆژی یان دیزاین و هیچ لیکۆئێنەوهیەک نەسەر ئەم بابەتە له هەریەم کوردستان ئەنجام نەدراوه. بۆیه توێژینەوهی ئێستا کاربەگەری پێداچوونەوه دواى فیدبای چاکسازی نووسراو نەسەر باشترکردنی وردبینی نووسینی خوێندکارانی بەکالۆریۆسی زمانی ئینگلیزی و ئایا دەتوانرێت ئەم کاربەگەرییە بگوازێتەوه بۆ پارچە نووسینە نوێیەکان دەکوئیتەوه. جگه نەوهش، لیکۆئێنەوه نەوه دەکات که ئایا جۆره جیاوازهکانی تاییهتەمەندی ریزمانی (نامازی ناسین، ریکهوتنی بکهه و کار، و قۆمی کار) به یهکسانی له ژیر کاربەگەری پراکتیکی پێداچوونەوهدان یان نا. زیاترتیروانیی مامۆستای بابەتەکه سەبارەت بە پرۆسەى پێداچوونەوه و کاربەگەرییەکانی نەسەر ئەدای نووسینی خوێندکاران دەکوئیتەوه. بۆ گەیشتن بەم نامانجانە، توێژینەوهکه دیزاینیکی شیوازی تیکهلاوی بۆ کوکردنەوه و شیکردنەوهی زانیارییەکان بەکارهیناوه. داتای چەندایەتی به بەکارهینانی دیزاینیکی نێمچه تاقیکاری کوکرایهوه که تیايدا 50 خوێندکاری قۆناعی دووهمی زمانی ئینگلیزی له زانکۆیهکی حکومی هەریەم کوردستانی عێراق وەک چارهسەر (پێداچوونەوهیان به نووسینەکانیان کرد نەسەر بنەمای فیدبای چاکسازی نووسراو) و گروپی کوئترۆل (تەنها پشکنینی فیدبای چاکسازی نووسراویان بەبێ پشکنین) دەستتیشانکران پێداچوونەوه به نووسینەکانیان). دواى چارهسەرکردنەکه، چاوپێکەوتنیکى نێمچه پیکهاتهی له گەڵ مامۆستای بابەتەکه ئەنجامدرا بۆ دەستەبەرکردنی زانیارییە چۆنایەتییهکان. داتاکان به بەکارهینانی SPSS و شیکاری بابەتی شیکرانهوه. ئەنجامی قۆناعی چەندایەتی دەرکەوت که پێداچوونەوه به ئەرکهکانی نووسیندا وردبینی ریزمانی نووسینی زمانی دووهمیان بەرز دەکاتەوه و کاربەگەرییەکهی له پارچە نووسینە نوێیەکاندا به تێپەربوونی کات بەردهوام دەبیت. دۆزینەوهیەکی دیکه نەوه بوو که ناستی کاربەگەری پێداچوونەوه له تاییهتەمەندییەکی ریزمانییهوه بۆ تاییهتەمەندییەکی دیکه جیاواز بوو. ئەم پهیوهندییهدا، هەر وهها له داتا چۆنایەتییهکانهوه گەیشته نەوه ئەنجامهی که داواکردن له خوێندکاران بۆ پێداچوونەوه کاربەگەر له پەرۆههکردنی بەشداریکردن و پالنهه بۆ هەردوو خوێندکار و مامۆستا. ئەم توێژینەوهیه بەشداره له هۆشیارکردنەوهی لایهنه پهیوهندیدارهکان سەبارەت به چۆنیهتی تیکه لکردن و بەکارهینانی فیدبای و پێداچوونەوهی چاکسازی نووسراو له پرۆسەى پەرۆههدهدا.

وشەى سەرەکی: فیدبای چاکسازی نووسراو، پێداچوونەوه، وردبینی ریزمانی، مامۆستایان، خوێندکاران.